

Heathers 11

Yearbook of The Heather Society 2014

Publication supported by
The Bowerman Charitable Trust

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ISSN 0440-5757

The Heather Society
c/o Tippitiwitchet Cottage, Hall Road, Outwell, Wisbech

Calluna vulgaris cv ~~'Maiden Blush'~~
'Trinklet'

5TH JUNE 1972

Found on Trink Hill, Cornwall.
The Newgrowth was cream,
succulent with red in the
interior tissue glowing through.
It appeared to be growing
out of a larger *Calluna*.

1ST. JULY

The red pigment has now
disappeared the texture
of the cream seemed papery,
some parts were dying off,
giving a somewhat tatty
appearance. However new
green growth started to
appear through the cream

29th. JULY

Took cuttings of new
green growth about 12.
Also 3 cream

19 Sept.

All cuttings have taken,
except the cream

23 SEPT.

Potted off cuttings

Richard Alfred Ide (1918–1981)

MIKE IDE

148 Tavistock Road, FLEET, Hampshire.

My father, Dick Ide, was born on 6 January 1918 at Old Alresford in Hampshire and the family moved to Merrow in Surrey shortly afterwards. He married Elsie Ruth Hart in 1940. Dick did a spell of sign-writing but never earned very much money. There was a story that he nearly became a millionaire over night. He discovered a painting in the loft of the house he was staying in and knowing a bit about art thought it could be a Turner. His best friend at the time had connections with art dealers and offered to take it to London to get it valued. Dick never saw him again.

He served in the Second World War as a Territorial but unfortunately was taken prisoner at Dunkirk and interned in a Polish prisoner-of-war camp whence I believe he was liberated by the Russians before the end of the war. Dick would never talk about the war, so details are sketchy. He did use his artistic skills to design and paint scenery for the camp plays.

Elsie and Dick set up home at a smallholding in a wooden building in Jocks Lane, Binfield, Berkshire, where they kept chickens, rabbits and ducks and bred bull terriers. Their attempt at breeding chickens came to an end when all except one were killed when the hutch caught fire one night. They had gypsies living

either side of them, and perhaps this was how Dick first got introduced to heather. He grew fruit, and Elsie transported the produce by pushing it in a pram three miles into Bracknell and there sold it to a greengrocer. They spent three harsh winters in Binfield, 1947 being particularly cold. Their two children, Penny (March 1946) and Mike (December 1947) were born there. The Bracknell area was beginning to be developed at the time, and they received a compulsory purchase order to move as the land they occupied was going to be built on.

The family moved into the more comfortable brick terrace house in the village of Binfield at Rose Hill. Here Dick had an allotment at the bottom of the garden where he spent the weekends enthusiastically growing vegetables.

He commuted to London daily, catching the train from Bracknell which was four miles away. Elsie had to drive him to the station in their beloved Morris 8, which Dick cherished but never drove. Rust under the car was a constant worry for him and we'd have family outings on a Sunday afternoon to a remote part the countryside armed with rust-remover, wire brush and some magic gunk that was lovingly applied to the chassis to prevent the rust returning. Most families drove out for a picnic.

He worked as an art director in a London advertising agency, Lucien Advertising, where he was responsible for developing campaigns for brands, well known at the time, including Real Brooke Shirts, Ye Olde Oak Ham, Bullworker (the chest expander that you caught the hairs of your chest in) and Harry Fenton Boutiques.

The next move was into Bracknell, opposite the station, which made life a lot easier. This house had quite a large garden, front and back, which sloped from top to bottom – hence the name Uplands – with room for vegetables and scope for developing his skills on a patio that had numerous rock-plants growing in the gaps. Dick started taking an interest in fungi and used to go foraging in the woods for edible mushrooms. We were not confident in his expertise in identifying them, although they looked and smelled delicious. We are not sure if he ate the mushrooms himself.

In 1961 he suffered a heart attack but recovered well enough to continue working and gardening. He loved his job but advertising being a very social career meant spending more time down the pub than working, resulting in him bringing his work home and locking himself away for hours putting ideas to paper. His talents enabled him to indicate type-faces, visualize images and come up with conceptual ideas.

Dick Ide, (right) in his heather garden at Wing House with granddaughter Kate.

He also found time to design furniture including concepts for the first sofa bed and had prototype models made. Dick had a passion for cooking and I remember his experiments with Chinese cooking in the Sixties. My father also used to make cheese, yoghurt and beer, and loved photography, developing his films and printing in the dark room.

1968: yet another compulsory purchase order. The beloved Uplands was to be pulled down to make way for a bus station. This led to a move to Wing House, on Upper Chobham Road in Camberley. Wing House was “exactly what it says on the tin”: the wing of a very large house. Dick fell in love with it straight away as it had a very big garden. His immediate thought was to lay out a lawn but eventually decided against it because of a large patch of self-sown *Calluna* which was cut back and “looked marvellous”. So this was when he developed his passion for heathers, and a lot of this huge garden was planted with heathers.

By this time, Penny was no longer living in the family house and Mike was attending Art School proudly following his father’s footsteps. Dick and Elsie loved Dorset, Devon and Cornwall and used to drive to Carbis Bay near St Ives in May every year. Bored of sitting on the beach, they used to go walking over the moors. Elsie remembers Dick on his hands and knees a lot, “spy glass” in hand, poring over a heather. He carried a duffel bag with plastic bags in it and

Sketch of *Erica cinerea* 'Rock Ruth' by Dick Ide.

would regularly take a cutting or three (see a facsimile of Dick's handwritten notes about cuttings, pp 5 & 6). These were then researched and grown on at Wing House, and were often given "private" names.

Dick and Elsie became members of The Heather Society in 1972, in time to be listed in the 1973 yearbook. Dick evidently had correspondence with David McClintock, who admitted he had never been to the Ides' garden and had only met Dick Ide once. However, as an assiduous recorder of cultivars, David did glean information from Dick about the heathers they had found in Cornwall, publishing the names in various issues of the Society's *Yearbook*. One of these was 'Ide's Double'; it was described by Dick in the Autumn 1977 *Bulletin*. Finds were not confined to heathers. In 1970, Elsie and Dick noticed a variegated plantain growing between the rocks of a boundary wall: "we rescued it from its perilous position" and planted it in a corner of the garden reserved

Cuttings

Time - July & August - June for E. carnea
 half ripe. Sometimes, every shoot on the
 plant must be used, so instead of tip cuttings,
 lower & flowering shoots - not woody can
 be used - usual length of cutting is 1"
 can use $\frac{1}{2}$ " upwards. Cuttings may be inserted
 up to one-third of their length in the
 rooting medium - up to 250 cuttings can
 be inserted in a 1" pot - no firming is needed
 watering from with fine rose is
 sufficient. - use a solution of potassium
 Permanganate to prevent damping
 off.

Preferable to use bottom heat
 - not essential.

High humidity accompanied by
 moderately high temperature.

It is where the cutting has a cool
 top due to the evaporation of moisture
 from top of the propagating material,
 a misty middle due to the humid condition
 in the frame, & a warm base from the
 propagating media often warmed by
 heating cables, that rooting is quickest.
 The usual temperature is 60° - 65° air
 temperature, 70° - 75° compost &
 bottom temperature

Rooting Media

A well-mixed compost of equal
 parts peat & $\frac{1}{2}$ " in grit is suitable

Portable method of propagating cuttings

Take a strip of polythene about
 2" deep line it out with sphagnum moss
 (moist) insert cuttings in moss & roll up
 place on bed of damp sphagnum,
 the tips of cuttings protrude from top -
 See illustration, ~~Some of~~ some of the
 soil from around the peath from which
 cuttings have been taken can be sprinkled
 in the moss

Once cuttings are well rooted + ~~this~~ depending on whether the rooting medium is rich enough to grow on the cuttings or if rooted in sand they must be potted off - peat pots or Jiffy pots are best for this, the tops should be pinched out a week before potting up

Calluna vulgaris 'Ide's Double' (E.C. Nelson)

for cuttings. Gradually slicing away the entirely green parts, Dick nursed this plantain and by 1974 had good plants to show to the Scientific Committee of the Royal Horticultural Society. Eventually he had about 40 plants and it was named 'Streaker' (Ide 1978).

The lounge walls would often be covered with his notes and sketches thankfully his loving wife didn't object. Among them were initial designs for The Heather Society's logo.

In 1981 Dick had a hernia operation and it was while he was recovering at home Elsie came home from work to find him collapsed on the floor. He had had a massive heart attack, and died. It is such a shame that he did not have any retirement time to pursue his interests. Who knows where they would have taken him?

The Heather Society's logo designed by Dick Ide first appeared (in black on white) on the title-page of the 1975 *Yearbook*, replacing the badge of the Royal Horticultural Society which had hitherto been used (because The Heather Society was affiliated to the RHS). This version (left) of the logo was created using the computer programme Photoshop, changing foliage to green.

The logo was subsequently transformed into the Society's distinctive badge by John Bridgland (see *Bulletin of The Heather Society* **2** (8): 4 (Summer 1976); **2** (10): 5–6 (Spring 1977)).

Further reading & sources

- IDE, R. A., 1977. A new double. *Bulletin of The Heather Society* **2** (12: incorrectly numbered 10): 3.
 IDE, R. A., 1978. *Plantago lanceolata* 'Streaker'. *The garden* **103**: 37.
 JONES, A. W., 1984. Heather cultivars from Cornwall. *Yearbook of The Heather Society* **3** (2): 50–56.
 McCLINTOCK, D., 1986. R. A. Ide (1918–1981) – a memoir. *Yearbook of The Heather Society* **3** (4): 13–16.
 SMALL, D. & SMALL, A., 2001 *Handy guide to heathers*. Creeping St Mary.

Heathers collected and named by R. A. Ide: descriptions derived from D. Small and A. Small, *Handy guide to heathers* (and the *International register of heather names*).

CALLUNA VULGARIS

'Ide's Double'

- Flowers double, heliotrope (H12), August–October; foliage green; similar to 'Tib'; 40 × 55cm.
- Seedling, probably from 'Ruth Sparkes'; found at Camberley, Surrey, in autumn 1974, among a group of 'Ruth Sparkes'; propagated in 1975 and introduced by R. A. Ide about 1976.
- *The Heather Society bulletin* **2** (12): 3 (1977); *Yearbook of The Heather Society* **2** (8): 47, 56 (1979); **3** (4): 13–16 (1986).

Calluna vulgaris **Mickkle-Dickkle**

A wildling we rescued high on one of Cornish hills, he was scruffy with knots of tightly packed foliage, disorganised, lumpy and obviously a dwarf

We carried him home and planted him by the edge of the crazy path among our self-sown *C.v.s*.

He responded by throwing out some slender new growth.

We think he is a quite a character, and have potted him up and ^{will} bring him in for the winter.

Will take cuttings next year

‘Low-low’: after the habit

- Prostrate plant, with pink flowers.
- Found at Mullion Cove, Cornwall, in June 1972.
- *Yearbook of The Heather Society* **3** (2): 53 (1984); ___ **3** (4): 14 (1986) [as ‘Low-low’]; T. L. Underhill, *Heaths & heathers*: 153 (1990; 2nd edn); D. McClintock, *Heathers of The Lizard*: 9 (1998).

‘Mickle Dickle’ (for Dick Ide’s original notes and illustrations, see p. 9)

® C.2012:05: registered on 30 October 2012 by Mike Ide, Fleet, Hampshire.

- Flowers lavender, late summer; low-growing.
- Found “high on one of Cornish hills” in the 1970s; propagated by John Hall in 2012.
- *Heathers* **10**: 82 (2013).

‘Penny Bun’: after Penny Ide (now Buck), and the bun-shaped habit.

- Pink (H8) flowers, August–September; foliage mid-green; vigorous but compact; 15 × 40cm.
- Found among stone chippings in a disused quarry near Leedstown, Cornwall, about 1972; introduced by P. G. Zwijnenburg (Boskoop, Netherlands).
- *Yearbook of The Heather Society* **2** (5): 56 (1976); ___ **3** (2): 53 (1984); ___ **3** (4): 13–16 (1986); T. L. Underhill, *Heaths & heathers*: 163 (1990; 2nd edn).

‘Red Rug’: alluding to the habit and the colour the young growth.

- Flowers pink, August–October; has red tips in spring; prostrate; 10 × 40cm.
- Found at Trink Hill near St Ives, Cornwall, in 1972.
- *Yearbook of The Heather Society* **2** (9): 65 (1980); ___ **3** (2): 53 (1984).

‘Trinklet’ (for Dick Ide’s original notes and illustrations, see frontispiece, p. ii)

- Young growth cream and pink; mauve (H2) flowers, September; compact; 10 × 25cm.
- Found on Trink Hill, Cornwall, on 5 June 1972; sent to Harlow Carr in 1974.
- *Yearbook of The Heather Society* **2** (6): 50 (1977); ___ **3** (2): 53 (1984); ___ **3** (4): 13–16, 41 (1986); G. P. Vickers (editor), *Heather trials 1971–75*: 19 (1976); *Heather trials 1976–81*: 4 (1983).
- Originally Dick Ide had suggested the name “Maiden’s Blush”.

ERICA CINEREA

‘Rock Ruth’ (see p. 4): named after Elsie Ruth Ide.

- Purple (H10) flowers, August–October; foliage dark green; far-spreading, prostrate; 10 × 30cm.
- Found at Mullion Cove, Cornwall, on 6 October 1972; introduced by P. G. Zwijnenburg (Boskoop),
- *Yearbook of The Heather Society* **2** (5): 56 (1976); ___ **3** (2): 54 (1984); ___ **3** (4): 13–16 (1986); ___ 1998: 7; *Dendroflora* **32**: 65 (1995); D. McClintock, *Heathers of The Lizard*: 8–9 (1998).

‘Romantic Muxoll’: a new St Dabeoc’s heath

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Why double flowers are so desirable I cannot explain. Most roses are bred double. Double-flowered ling cultivars are popular, too. Otherwise, double-flowered heathers are very uncommon, partly because no one has tried breeding such plants.

One double-flowered St Dabeoc’s heath has been grown for more than 30 years. ‘Charles Nelson’ was found by Charles Nelson in the wild in Connemara in 1978. Fortunately, this double-flowered cultivar begins the season with a few single flowers and that property makes it possible to raise seed-progeny from ‘Charles Nelson’ and create new double varieties.

For the past 17 years I worked on this and, at last, the first man-made double-flowered cultivar of *Daboecia cantabrica* has come on the market: ‘Romantic Muxoll’. The last part of the name is my mother’s family name. My own family name is not easy for English-speaking people to pronounce!

Despite the assertion that ‘Charles Nelson’ begins the season with single flowers with fertile stamens, in my garden it usually begins with totally double flowers (without stamens) and hence I have no possibility of harvesting pollen. However, in 1996, where I first got the idea about breeding more double-flowered St Dabeoc’s heaths, I was lucky. Despite the very first flowers being double, a very few petals had the upper edges turned in a little and so were carrying a tiny amount of pollen.

‘Charles Nelson’ has nearly pendulous flowers, so I selected ‘White Blum’ with the ascending flowers as recipient for the pollen in order to make it easy to see the doubling in any progeny. From this first attempt at pollination with the very scarce pollen I harvested 35 seeds in the autumn. I germinated them during the winter under lights. I cannot remember how many seedlings came up, but not all of the seeds germinated. Late in the summer they flowered. None were double, and none had ascending flowers.

I was disappointed, but not surprised. I had read a book about plant breeding used in the education of nurserymen (I am a pharmacist) so I knew that some properties only appear in a plant if it has received the same characteristics from both its mother and father. I had to control my impatience until the next

year. I pollinated my self-made seedlings with each other - there was plenty of pollen because the stamens were fertile and, later, plenty of seeds because these flowers also have a fully functioning pistil.

The following summer the second-generation plants flowered, some hundred plants, and a minority of them (about one in every five) had double flowers. Some had only a second ring of petals, but others were fully double. Again, only a minority of the doubles had ascending flowers. Many looked rather poor.

As far as I can remember, it was the following year when I discovered 'Romantic Muxoll' among several hundred plants. "Discovered" because that plant was the only one which shed most of its faded flowers. Two others shed a smaller proportion of their old flowers. This very worthwhile property is new, because 'Charles Nelson' never sheds its withered flowers.

I discarded my first generation crosses believing that I would be able to harvest some pollen from 'Romantic Muxoll' the next year. To my huge disappointment 'Romantic Muxoll' did not produce any single flowers, with fertile stamens, at the beginning of the following summer. Thus I could not try to breed seedlings which would shed most of the faded flowers.

Having grown 'Romantic Muxoll' under different conditions, both indoors and outside, for eight years, waiting for single flowers at the start of the flowering season, I asked Charles Nelson if he could help me with growing 'Romantic Muxoll' in England where *Daboecia* 'Charles Nelson' seemingly always had single flowers at the beginning of the summer. Charles connected me to a helpful nurseryman in Cornwall and a keen, helpful Heather Society member in western Ireland. They both grew 'Romantic Muxoll' for a year – no single flowers, and no trace of pollen!

Recently Kurt Kramer, in Germany, has told me that he has found single flowers with his 'Romantic Muxoll'. At first I could hardly believe it, but now I look forward to receiving pollen from Kurt (if 'Romantic Muxoll' produces single flowers again). I am not sure if its pollen will "transfer" the propensity to shed the old flowers to other double-flowered varieties, but it is the logical step.

Note

A small number of 'Romantic Muxoll' were available from Forest Edge Nursery in the spring of 2013. Other wholesale heather nurseries in Germany (Hiedl, Marohn & Häger), Holland (Heathers Heide), Scotland (Spring Park Nursery) and Denmark (Gl. Sunds Planteskole) received 'Romantic Muxoll' plants a year or two after Forest Edge Nursery.

The mechanical pruning of heathers

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Heathers have to be pruned from time to time, so that they keep vigorous and grow bushy. In the wild, at least in northern Germany, heather is trimmed by a variety of short-tailed sheep called Heidschnucken and rejuvenates in this way naturally. It is obvious that sheep cannot be used for trimming in a modern nursery containing hundreds of thousands of heathers. Furthermore, pruning every single plant by hand is too expensive. That is why machines are used.

A flock of moorland sheep – Heidschnucken – on the heath at Schneverdingen in February 2006. Moorland sheep are a self-sufficient breed. (© 2006 ArtMechanic. Source Wikipedia Commons.)

In making use of machines, some points have to be taken into account. The plants should have grown uniformly and then stand on a flat surface. In addition it is important to cultivate upright-growing varieties. If they are too flat, the machine cannot reach every shoot so that the plants have to be cut back by hand.

Daboecia cantabrica 'Andrea' (interspersed with willows), trimmed two weeks before (front), one week ago (middle) and three weeks ago (distance).

My cultivar 'Andrea' is a good example of a *Daboecia* which is easy to prune. Unfortunately it grows too upright and becomes very leggy. The conspicuous and much-in-demand GARDEN GIRLS® selections 'Nelly' and 'Claire' are hardly produced because they cannot be trimmed mechanically. Their shoots hang down so no machine can reach them.

Calluna vulgaris plants are trimmed between four and six times, depending on the variety, size and weather conditions. The first two cuttings are made with normal hedge clippers. Boxes containing the young plants are slid under the hanging hedge-clippers. The cropped shoots are collected and used as cuttings to produce plants for sale the following year.

The trimmed plants are re-potted into bigger pots. The next trimmings are done on the nursery fields. Lawn mowers, hung in a rig, are driven above the plants. They receive a clean cut, as long as the blades of the mower are sharp and the young plants are not too tall. The accumulating waste is blown into a basket behind the lawn mower. Providing the plants can dry after being pruned, a fungicide treatment is not necessary afterwards.

Trimming *Daboecia cantabrica* in bloom: they will blossom again in two to three weeks ready for sale.

Trimming *Calluna vulgaris*

A special case is the pruning of *Daboecia* that are already in full bloom. Having been trimmed back, the plants will bloom again in three to six weeks, depending on the variety. Thus, the time of sale can be changed, which might be necessary if the demand is too low.

At the present time I am breeding and selecting *Daboecia* which will blossom early in the season. The start of blooming can be controlled with a cut during mid-summer, similar to ‘Andrea’. This procedure is not possible with late-blooming varieties because they cannot recover quickly enough after the cut.

Trimming ‘Albert’s Gold’

This year was the first time we used “Supercut 2000”, a gas-operated, fast-cutting hedge-clipper, to prune our *Erica arborea*. ‘Albert’s Gold’ had grown too tall, so we cut them back by hanging the “Supercut” on a trolley which normally is used to irrigate plants. Once again, the accumulating waste is blown into a basket. Normally we use the “Supercut” to harvest cuttings from different heathers. Indeed, it was invented by the tea industry to enable tea to be harvested much more quickly.

The “golden years” for heathers: some personal reflections

GEOFFREY YATES

WINDERMERE, Cumbria

This is an extended, illustrated version of “Some memories of The Heather Society” published in *Heathers* 10: 11–13 (2012).

When I look round the garden centres and nurseries, read the gardening press with articles written by gardening “personalities” some of whom actually go into print or on the air saying “I hate heathers”, I feel privileged to have been involved with heathers in the 1960s through to the 1980s. Whilst I accept that styles change, how anybody can write an article about favourite winter plants, illustrated with a picture of dead grasses and perennials, without any heathers in sight, as Joe Swift did recently in a national paper, is really beyond my comprehension. As for the modern-day Chelsea show-gardens with conceptual this and that, hard-landscaping costing many thousands, and with BBC programmes concentrating on the same gardens and designers Obviously I am getting old!

Jennifer and I made a garden in the 1960s which included a water-garden built into a large area excavated by the previous owner for a tennis court. Taking advantage of the slopes, it included a stream, emerging from underground, flowing down waterfalls into the pond. The area around the water source was planted with heathers in a symbolic depiction of an underground source of water appearing above ground on a moorland, and they were the plants which inspired my interest. In those days this country was blessed with numerous specialist heather nurseries as well as all the big household names such as Hilliers, Blooms, Notcutts, Treseders, Ingwersens, James Smith of Tansley ... just to name a few, all featuring heathers prominently in their catalogues. Ireland and Scotland had equally prominent firms also listing numerous cultivars – Slieve Donard Nursery, for example – and every alpine specialist featured heathers in the lists. My first interest (it could be said obsession) was getting all the catalogues, which was a revelation to me at that time, and I kept these until a few years ago when I passed them to the Society.

Every firm had its own introductions, but many trails led back to Maxwell & Beale and, to a lesser extent, to Underwoods of Woking. The real star of the

Figure 1. Foxhollow: a pen-and-ink drawing (signed Langdon) from John F. Letts's *Handbook of hardy heaths and heathers* (August 1966) (see Figure 4, p. 23).

pack at that time was John F. Letts in Windlesham who had produced a very polished catalogue and book, with a wonderful show-garden to see on a visit to him. At any time of year his garden was a picture, always immaculate, and most importantly easily maintained. I was hooked. John Letts probably did as much as anybody to popularize heather gardens. The Proudleys were also quite prominent in those days.

Acid sandy soil in our garden was ideal for heathers of all types, and inspired by John Letts we made a large heather garden and because of local interest started to propagate plants for sale at church and village hall and at fund-raising events many of which were held in our garden. Obviously the quality of the plants we produced was acceptable because local nurseries asked us to grow for them, which was the start of Tabramhill Gardens.

The tremendous interest in heathers at that time inspired me to seek out true stock of all the cultivars listed in Fred Chapple's book as well as Lett's catalogue and other publications of that era. As a result we obtained plants from every nursery in the country which listed heathers and what a confusion that revealed. Just as an example we obtained 16 different plants labelled *Erica vagans* 'Mrs D. F. Maxwell', and a similar number labelled 'St Keverne'. Tracking down

Figure 2. Cover of a catalogue from Frank Hamer's Sunnymount Nursery, Marple Bridge, Cheshire (from G. Yates's collection).

heather nursery called Sunnymount Nursery at Marple Bridge in Cheshire run by Frank Hamer, an engineer by profession, who had collected every heather introduced in the 1930s and propagated them each year throughout the Second World War growing them on as open-ground plants in his garden, so he was a wonderful source of reliably named cultivars of the pre-war era. It was probably the nicest nursery I ever saw because he planted them out ornamentally as a heather garden and dug them up if you bought plants from him. Amongst many others I remember finding with him was *C. vulgaris* 'Walter Ingwersen' (then called 'Elegantissima'). Will Ingwersen at the family nursery of that name insisted that because it was not completely hardy the cultivar bearing his father's name was extinct having died out during the war years. On a visit to Marple Bridge I saw plants growing under that name, bought stock and sent it to Ingwersen who admitted the following year when it flowered that it was the true plant. There were many similar experiences thanks to the small specialist

propagating material true to name was an exciting and very worthwhile experience, of which more later.

Another challenge was to find cultivars apparently lost to cultivation. This was an interest shared with several members of The Heather Society's Northern Group which had been formed by John Ardron and met at Harlow Carr. It was John's inspiration, supported by many others including (to name just a few) Peter Vickers, Albert Julian, Des Oliver, and Hugh Prew who enlisted the enthusiastic help of Geoffrey Smith, then Curator of Harlow Carr, to establish The Heather Society trials. I can remember Des Oliver tracking down *Calluna vulgaris* 'Bransdale White' which had been found on the

North York Moors, and this was one of many such discoveries by various people. There was a lovely small

nurseries, nearly all one-man-bands, which propagated fresh stock every year taking great care over naming. The confusion that had developed was caused by the larger, very commercial nurseries using inexperienced staff with little interest in plants being true to name. The problem was by no means confined to heathers! The Heather Society trials at Harlow Carr owed a great deal to the discovery of these old cultivars from reliable sources.

Fascinating in many ways, but a nightmare in others, was the proliferation of numerous “new” varieties from all corners of Europe, either from collections in the wild or chosen from the many seedlings that grew in established heather gardens. Most of the specialist nurseries had introductions chosen by them, and also cultivars named by enthusiasts. Some were outstanding, others good, and many little or no different to old, established cultivars. All this was before

St Kilda White Heather

These plants are grown from cuttings of plants taken from the National Trust for Scotland's St. Kilda Islands and are entirely distinct from mainland heather due to isolation and extreme exposure. 5p. of each heather plant sold is donated to the National Trust for Scotland St. Kilda Fund as a contribution towards preserving this spectacular island group.

To plant, REMOVE POT and PLANT DEEP in open free soil about 12" apart. Add peat if obtainable and mulch or TOP-DRESS WITH plenty of peat or SAW-DUST.

Pot Plants should not be over-watered or allowed to dry out. Keep in an open sunny position.

Do not use manure or use fertiliser.

Figure 3. Information slip about the St Kilda heathers (from G. Yates's collection).

the days of deliberate hybridizing as now carried out by Kurt Kramer in Germany and Dr John Griffiths in Yorkshire. As far as I am aware all the new introductions in the era I am writing about were natural, unassisted crosses or plants found on moorland in natural stands of heather much in the same way as D. F. Maxwell found the famous Cornish heath named by him. Others cropped up as natural seedlings in heather gardens. A very good example of natural finds was the St Kilda collection by Bob Brien of Pitcairngreen, Perth, which he named after the various islands in the St Kilda group. The very dwarf habit of these cultivars stayed just as compact even when the selected plants were

cultivated in normal gardens. Bob was one of great personalities of the heather world who was nearly always in full Highland dress whenever you met him, and on his nursery he had large stocks for sale of his white-flowered St Kilda “Boreray” for the benefit of tourists wanting lucky white heather. Nearby was a small batch labelled “True ‘Boreray’” for the heather enthusiast! The true one was much more difficult to propagate.

One of the other great characters in the heather fraternity was J. W. Sparkes of Beoley in Worcestershire. I never visited his nursery, but by the time I had become interested he was already well known as the raiser of new cultivars. ‘Beoley Gold’, ‘Peter Sparkes’, ‘Joan Sparkes’, ‘Robert Chapman’, ‘Sir John Charrington’ and ‘Ann Sparkes’ were all introduced by him, and featured in every nursery list in the 1960s. He continued to introduce new selections which I am certain were all natural variations rather than the result of any deliberate breeding programme as he had a very keen eye for good seedlings and sports from existing cultivars. When Tabramhill Gardens had become established he approached me about introducing some of his new finds such as ‘Beechwood Crimson’, ‘Beoley Crimson’, ‘Beoley Silver’, ‘Silver Knight’ and several others, the idea being that we should buy trays of rooted cuttings from him. The problem was that he rooted his cuttings in a most peculiar mixture of bracken mould which worked as far as rooting was concerned, but it was impossible to wean the cuttings to grow on in more standard, soil-less, peat composts. Eventually we had to supply him with trays filled with our own rooting mix which he duly returned in due course full of rooted cuttings. Joe Sparkes and his son Peter were indeed memorable characters amongst many others in the heather world at that time.

Fred Chapple who was President of The Heather Society was still very active in those days, living on the Isle of Man but taking a very full part in the various meetings and events. He was still an enthusiastic finder of plants and his new ones were usually introduced through Slieve Donard Nursery in Northern Ireland or Kirby Nursery on the Isle of Man, and the *Calluna* cultivars ‘Leslie Slinger’, ‘Ruby Slinger’ and ‘Calf of Man’, amongst others, came from him. Kirby Nursery introduced ‘Kirby White’, probably a Fred Chapple find as it is very similar to ‘Ruby Slinger’. Another heather man of the pre-war era, P. S. Patrick, was a great source of history having worked for Maxwell & Beale in the 1930s, and he came to Heather Society meetings from time to time. His knowledge enabled us to source true ‘Mrs D. F. Maxwell’ and

‘St Keverne’ as cuttings from plantings made by Maxwell & Beale when he worked for them. The Heather Society trials at Harlow Carr brought together the most comprehensive collection of cultivars that has probably ever existed since 1946 as even the specialist nurseries only carried a selection of what they regarded as the most garden-worthy choices. I am sure it is fair to say that every available cultivar at that time was included and all the new introductions were added for several years. The performance of each was much affected by the soil conditions on the trial ground and some did not do as well as might have been expected. Nevertheless it was a very fair test which, generally speaking, sorted out the better growers from the others. The report still makes interesting reading although probably irrelevant in the present-day limited market despite the fact that many of the then popular cultivars have been superseded by new introductions, many of which are in no way superior to many of the old ones.

It is probably worthwhile to list a few more nurseries which highlighted heathers in their catalogues or were purely heather nurseries.

Figure 4. Cover of John F. Lett's *Handbook of hardy heaths and heathers* (1966).

Figure 5. Cover of one of the Proudleys' catalogues (from G. Yates's collection).

Jack Drake in Aviemore, a wonderful alpine nursery, introduced *Daboecia* × *scotica* nos. 1, 2 and 3, raised by William Buchanan in Glasgow. No. 1 was eventually named ‘Jack Drake’, and no. 3 became ‘William Buchanan’. He also raised *Calluna* ‘Inshriach Bronze’, named after his nursery. Another outstanding alpine nursery, Edrom, introduced *Daboecia* × *scotica* ‘Bearsden’ and ‘Silverwells’. Jack Stitt of Blairgowrie, a retired soldier who had spent the war as a Japanese prisoner-of-war working on the bridge over the River Kwai, introduced *Erica carnea* ‘Adrienne Duncan’; Delaney & Lyle *Calluna* ‘Bud Lyle’; and there were many others such as Oliver & Hunter, J. R. Ponton, W. Moss in North Wales of *D. cantabrica* ‘David Moss’; Jack Brummage in Norfolk who was responsible for *E. carnea* ‘Myretoun Ruby’ and *E.* × *darleyensis* ‘Jack H. Brummage’. I apologize to any that I have missed out. These small nurseries were the fabric of heather growing in these “golden years” although many others joined in when the commercial potential became clear. Heathers were very big business in the nurseries and, later, in garden centres selling to the public. All of these nurseries produced catalogues of which John F. Letts’s and the Proudleys’ were probably the most glossy.

Plants go through fashions. Even roses had a bad patch some years ago and have since made a recovery, probably due to clever marketing by newer nurseries. Obviously the plethora of gardening “experts” writing books and appearing on television tends to dictate fashions, many of which I find very difficult to comprehend. I personally find dead perennials and grasses in the winter not only boring but also a complete mess to look out upon. Conifers so wonderfully promoted by Adrian Bloom many years ago which he associated with heathers to produce the most colourful and easily maintained all-the-year-round gardens went into decline, although conifers do seem to be making a slow comeback. I feel sure that heathers will do the same although the sooner garden centres stop selling unnamed plants and replace them with named cultivars the better, the quicker that recovery will be. In Germany heathers have been regarded as bedding plants for many years although there are also many outstanding heather gardens encouraged, and sometimes created, by the German Heather Society. Reading The Heather Society’s journal every year it is apparent that Canada and America have many outstandingly good gardens using heathers. It cannot be too long before somebody sees sense in this country and again makes much wider use of heathers.

Growing heathers on an alkaline soils for 43 years

DIANE H. JONES

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My husband (Bert Jones) and I joined The Heather Society in 1967 as a direct result of visiting John Letts's garden at Windlesham in Surrey. He was, as Geoffrey Yates points out in his article (pp 18–24), one of the leading growers of heathers in the Sixties. That garden was an inspiration, and it was from John Letts that we purchased our first heathers. We were then living in the Thames Valley at Taplow on neutral soil.

We began learning about how to grow and look after our plants, when in 1970 we moved to southeastern Somerset only to find the soil in the locality was on either limestone or chalk. The pH of our soil is between 8.0 and 8.3, so this was a challenge to establish a heather garden on alkaline soil. Fortunately, we had learnt that all heathers which flower between November and April or May are lime-tolerant – they are *Erica carnea* (winter heath) and *E. erigena* (Irish heath, or Mediterranean heath) and their hybrid *E. × darleyensis* (Darley Dale heath), as well as the lovely spring-flowering *E. × vietchii* 'Exeter' (Veitch's heath). These plants are all hardy. Our collection included a number of plants with interesting foliage colour, especially *E. carnea* cultivars.

For summer flower colour we have experimented and, sadly, found we could not grow *Erica vagans* (Cornish heath) because the soil is magnesium deficient. However, Bert became interested in *E. manipuliiflora* which originates in southern Europe (former Yugoslavia eastwards to Turkey) on limestone mountains and he travelled to the western portion of its occurrence with David McClintock in 1988. They brought back many cuttings which we propagated and distributed to other members of The Heather Society. As a result some excellent hybrids between *E. vagans* and *E. manipuliiflora* have been raised and introduced by Professor John Griffiths: *E. × griffithsii* (Griffiths's heath). I particularly like 'Valerie Griffiths', which John raised, and 'Jacqueline' which is of uncertain origin. Some of the original *E. manipuliiflora* clones also proved to be outstanding, including 'Cascades' which Bert named, and the recently named 'Bert Jones'.

For alkaline soils I also recommend the shrubby Corsican heath, *Erica terminalis* 'Thelma Woolner', which blooms from July until November, as well

Erica × williamsii ‘Ken Wilson’ was raised in Canada by David Wilson and is more floriferous than the wild-collected Cornish clones.

as *E. × arendsiana* ‘Charnwood Pink’ – a darker pink selection (‘Ronsdorf’) is also available but I do not have it. Arends’s heath blooms from October to March.

I can also successfully grow *Daboecia cantabriga* (St Dabeoc’s heath) cultivars, and a lovely low-growing plant for summer colour, *Erica × williamsii* ‘Ken Wilson’ (Williams’s heath).

I would be interested to know if any members have other success on alkaline soil, or have other difficulties.

Heather colour all year round can be achieved especially with the use of good foliage colours.

Do remember that heavy wet soils, like ours, need to be lightened with the addition of peat, leaf mould or sharp sand.

Unexpected lime tolerance in some cultivars

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Being blessed with a rich alkaline clay, not deficient in magnesium, I have tried to grow some of the less common hybrids to see if they could cope, giving them the benefit of the most free-draining bed in my garden.

Not all cultivars succeed as well as may be expected. An example is the beautiful *Erica* × *williamsii* ‘Ken Wilson’. Repeated attempts have all produced a poor flowering, weak plant. Conversely *Daboecia* × *scotica* ‘William Buchanan’ appears happy. *E.* × *arendsiana* ‘Charnwood Pink’ is coping and *E.* × *gaudifcans* ‘Edewecht Belle’, planted in 1997, is still blooming well although showing more pronounced yellowing of new foliage.

A clear success has been *Erica* × *krameri* ‘Rudi’ planted in 1999. This particular hybrid was thought to require an acid soil but this cultivar shows no sign of chlorosis and still flowers well. I also tried ‘Otto’ but that cultivar died early. I have not added iron chelates in any form, nor flowers of sulphur. The only factor that may be assisting their performance was the use of crushed granite in bed preparation: the biotite and other ferro-magnesian minerals may have encouraged beneficial mycorrhizal activity.

Erica × *krameri* ‘Rudi’, raised by Kurt Kramer by crossing *E. carnea* with the Balkan heath (*E. spiculifolia*), in Richard Canovan’s garden at Toothill. Its tolerance for lime must have been inherited from the winter heath (*E. carnea*). It is also very hardy, with fresh green foliage all the year. (E. C. Nelson)

Growing heathers on driveway hardcore in the East Anglian Fens

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When you venture into the wilds, more so in southern Europe than in Ireland or Britain, the places where heathers grow naturally are usually *not* bogs or moors sodden with moisture and spongy under foot. They are often very rocky with little or no soil covering, and in the middle of summer the heat is searing.

Erica manipuliflora: two plants growing on a massive boulder at Phalasarna in western Crete. Note the crack in which one plant is rooted. This is the parent plant of the now erect shrub in Tippitiwitchet Cottage (see p. 29, middle row, left)

The rocks can vary too. Several European species of *Erica* are found almost exclusively on limestones. Two in particular deserve more attention from gardeners: *Erica sicula* and *E. manipuliflora*.

Heathers (*Erica*) at Tippitiwitchet Cottage, Outwell.

Top row: (left) *E. manipuliiflora* 'Bert Jones' and (right) *E. erigena* 'Ivory'. Middle row: (left) *E. manipuliiflora* from Phalasarua, Crete, and (right) Corsican heath (*E. terminalis*) in bud. Bottom row: (left) *E. × oldenburgensis* 'Ammerland' and (right) *E. × arendsiana* 'Charnwood Pink'

However, as in the great limestone areas of Britain (Malham in Yorkshire, for example) and Ireland (The Burren), there are additional environmental characteristics that need to be kept in mind, as well as the presence of lime. Carboniferous limestones, like those in The Burren and Yorkshire, are naturally fractured – these fractures can range from microscopic cracks less than the width of a hair to a massive system of underground caverns and tunnels. Thus, water never lies on the surface of the landscape but very rapidly drains “into” the rock – the cracks, which heather roots can penetrate, can act as a moisture reservoir at the same time as ensuring very “sharp” drainage. Much the same happens on the volcanic gravels in the Azores.

Our driveway, composed of bits of broken bricks and concrete blocks, builder’s sand (the rusty brown stuff that is never recommended for use in opening up heavy soil), bits of drainage pipes and even wire and lumps of metal – in short everything left on the site when the house was finished about 25 years ago and then flattened and covered with loose rounded river-gravel – mimics these natural limestone outcrops. It may be most peculiar to try to garden on a driveway, but we don’t need parking spaces for half a dozen cars (which is what it almost amounted to). So, we excavated a hole, created a pond, made a small rockery, and, by digging holes elsewhere in the drive, created pockets for plants (we did leave room for the car!) – *Agapanthus* loves it; *Gladiolus byzantinus*, *Silene maritima* (sea-campion), *Origanum vulgare* (marjoram), *Sternbergia luteum*, the October-flowering snowdrop *Galanthus reginae-olgae*, and the winter-flowering *Iris lazica*, all thrive in this builder’s “muck”, seeding and spreading – the list is longer and includes *Cyclamen*, *Leucojum autumnalis* and a variant of Miss Willmott’s ghost (*Eryngium giganteum*) which Graham Stuart Thomas gave us (it’s now a weed!). And, some heathers ...

Erica erigena ‘W. T. Rackliff’, ‘Ivory’ and ‘Irish Silver’: I got ‘W. T. Rackliff’ from Denbeigh Heathers soon after Sue and I were married and I moved from Dublin in 1995. It grew to about 4 feet tall, but in the winter of 2010 was badly damaged by snow and so I cut it back severely, leaving some wisps of greenery. It has regenerated and is now back to 2 feet in height. ‘Ivory’ came from Phil Joyner – a strange plant that seems to want to form an inverted cone – and sulked for a few years beside an old ceramic sink. But in the past two years it has put on a spurt, and while not as shapely as ‘W. T. Rackliff’, it is now no longer sulking. ‘Irish Silver’ came from the late Arnold Stow: another oddity and apparently even slower to settle in and grow than ‘Ivory’.

Erica carnea ‘Saskia’: a recent acquisition from David Edge, and as there is nowhere else to grow it, it is also in the driveway. It bloomed very well the first year, and has budded for its second year. But I don’t prune, so it may get a bit straggly.

Erica × *oldenburgensis* ‘Ammerland’: this has the same history as ‘W. T. Rackliff’ including snow-damage and severe pruning. It re-sprouted even more vigorously than *E. erigena* and rewarded last spring with a good show of flowers which slowly change from almost white to a smokey pink. The red tips of the young shoots are sparse so they do not turn the plant scarlet – if they did ‘Ammerland’ would be spectacular.

Erica terminalis: I think this Corsican heath was an orphan from the plant sale at one of the annual gatherings, but I did not retain a record. It has no problem growing in the driveway “soil”, tending to bloom twice, once in June and July, and again in October: it is in full flower as I write this (16 October).

Erica manipuliiflora: I have two clones, one from Richard Canovan, which was one of those brought from Croatia by Bert Jones, and which now bears Bert’s name. It is a spectacular plant, producing very long slender shoots covered with pure white flowers. In a breeze, these shoots wave about so that this plant is not a static heather. I know of no other heather that has this character, although I can imagine that a vigorous plant of *E.* × *griffithsii* ‘Heaven Scent’ or ‘Jacqueline’ might perform the same way. Again, pruning is minimal – a hair-cut to reduce the height.

The second clone is a marked contrast, and as yet is not named. It came from a boulder in the middle of the archaeological site of Phalasarna on the north-west tip of Crete, within splashing distance of the sea. The original plant was completely prostrate, following the contours of the boulder and tightly filling the crevices with minuscule shoots. David Edge propagated it for me and gave me a plant that is now as stiffly erect as any heather could be. Alas, this also means the shoots are brittle and easily snapped. The flowers are bright lavender. It starts to bloom in late September and is now in full flower.

Erica × *arendsiana* ‘Charwood Pink’: a gift from the late Allen Hall, this took a little while to settle in. Allen’s plant was stiff and upright, displaying more of the characters of its Corsican heath parent than its bell heather (*E. cinerea*) one. It has flowers on it almost all the time, little, pale pink clusters at top the stems, but comes into fuller bloom about early November; it is now covered with buds.

The mature flowers of *Erica* × *oldenbergensis* ‘Ammerland’ are pink, contrasting beautifully with the pure white of *E. erigena* ‘W. T. Rackliff’: spring 2013, both recovered from their severe pruning to stumps.

I used to grow a few other heathers – *Erica umbellata* ‘David Small’ was happy in an old sink in a mixture of peat and very coarse gravel but those were special conditions, deliberately free of lime – and *E. × darleyensis* ‘J. W. Porter’ and ‘Margaret Porter’ exist under the clothes line in the “normal” garden soil (heavy clay) of our back garden (the soil here is a bit better than the driveway but it betrays its use in past centuries as the back yard of the local inn – we often find pits of pottery and clam shells). Looking back at photographs, I also must have had *E. manipuliflora* ‘Aldeburgh’, from Denbeigh Heathers, and I no longer recall why it perished.

If I could create a rock-garden, in a sunny place, with limestone slabs and sharp-draining gritty soil (but there isn’t such a place now at Tippitiwichee Cottage), I would plant in it *Daboecia azorica*, *Erica sicula* subsp. *bocquetii* and *E. multiflora*, for I am certain they need three things to thrive: a pinch of lime, very sharp drainage and permanent moisture. That is, the complete opposite of an Irish peat bog or a “normal” heather garden.

RHS Hampton Court Palace Flower Show 2013

BARRY SELLERS

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The Heather Society decided in 2012 to have a stand at the 2013 Royal Horticultural Society's flower show at Hampton Court Palace. This followed the very successful 2011 show, which saw the Society enter a garden in collaboration with the British Heather Growers Association, which won a prestigious Gold Medal.

The 2013 show took place from 9 to 14 July. The Heather Society along with the British Heather Growers Association put together a team of volunteers to prepare the Society's stand and take charge of advising the public on each of the five days of the event. The stand was located within a large marquee in the showground. The Heather Society's Chairman, David Edge, led the way with preparing the display stand with heathers from his nursery. He had travelled up to the showground on the Sunday prior to the opening to put together the stand. He was ably assisted by his manageress, Trish Hardy, and John Hall.

However, preparation for the display began back in 2011 with the concept for a stand at the Floral Marquee, taking inspiration from the award-winning garden at Hampton Court. For whilst chatting with exhibitors in the Marquee on that occasion David realised that it was possible to construct a display garden and additionally sell heathers, which was not possible with the garden back in 2011. Here was an opportunity to promote heathers both through a visual display and for people to have the opportunity to purchase the plants that they can see. This led to a plan whereby heathers from the wholesale nurseries of both John Hall and David Edge could be displayed on behalf of The Heather Society, without incurring any cost to the Society. However, being able to jointly sell heather plants they could cover their individual costs. In this way the promotion of both The Heather Society and heathers could be undertaken in a more cost-effective way, as well as being able to supply plants to the public.

Placing this concept before Council, it gained unanimous approval and David and John set out to proceed with this daunting task. The summer of 2012 saw David and John selecting a range of heather plants. These were then potted on to provide a mature stock for display.

Figure 1. The mock-up of the stand at Forest Edge Nurseries (© David Edge 2013).

The design for the garden for the stand was formulated in the “grey cells” to convey a distinct message to the public about the diversity of uses for heathers in the garden, the range available, as well as making the connection with the topical issue of bees and pollination.

He had designed the mini-garden for the Forest Edge Nurseries’ stand. It was a three dimensional display with the taller heathers to the back then sloping down to the lower growing cultivars to the front. A vertical tree stump at the back of the display not only reinforced the three dimensionality of the display and the natural appearance of the garden but was also decorated with *Calluna*. Towards the front, the low-growing heathers were carefully arranged in a natural garden setting with a moss covered tree carcass lying flat, defining a more open area in front with raked gravel peppered with individual plants. The raked gravel around the plants helped to emphasise the qualities of each individual plant.

At the front of the stand was the yellow-foliaged *Erica carnea* cultivars ‘Foxhollow’ and ‘Golden Starlet’, and the bronze-yellow ‘Anne Sparkes’.

In the middle ground, above the raked gravel area, were stands of *Erica tetralix* ‘Pink Star’, *E. cinerea* ‘Providence’, ‘Joseph Murphy’, ‘Lilac Time’ and ‘Goldilocks’, and *E. ciliaris* ‘David McClintock’.

At the front was also a terracotta pot in the shape of an urn with a display of *Calluna vulgaris* ‘Alba Rigida’. Another rectangular terracotta pot contained a mixture of *Erica cinerea* and *Calluna* cultivars. Yet another pot, a round green ceramic pot contained a plant of *E. × darleyensis* ‘Eva Gold’ that had been grown as a topiary subject with a single central stem carefully manicured foliage. The stand advertised The Heather Society.

Figure 2. Part of the stand at Hampton Court Palace Show (© David Edge 2013).

The exhibits by nurseries in the Floral Marquee were judged by the RHS. Forest Edge Nurseries received a prestigious Silver-Gilt Award. As a result David was interviewed for BBC television and the video that was broadcast showing David on the nursery talking about heathers and heather-growing has done much to give positive publicity about The Heather Society and the growing of heathers.

As the flower show opened each day a steady flow of people came into the tent and the heather garden became the focus of attention for photographers. Visitors would acknowledge the quality of the heather garden with congratulatory comments. Many would stop to ask questions about the garden, about growing heathers, and also how to acquire plants of those on display. By mid-morning of each day the throngs of people filled the tent, so much so that the crowd became tightly packed. With the temperature outside just over 30°C, it was even hotter inside. Bottles of cold water needed to be at the ready of those helping out at stands.

Phil Joyner

Figure 3. The media scrum, including BBC television presenter Joe Swift (in panama hat).

Figure 4. The Chairman, David Edge (right centre) and Honorary Treasurer, Richard Canovan (extreme right) on The Heather Society stand (Both Figures 3 & 4 © Phil Joyner 2013).

Questions asked by people included: “How do I grow heathers?” “What type of soil do I need?” “Can heathers grow in the shade?”

There were also many comments about the display, including: “You were robbed”. Another said, “The best garden in the whole show; even better than

the show garden”. “The stand is an ocean of tranquillity”; “A beautiful setting”; and “Well-deserved”, were other remarks.

By 7 o'clock of each evening the crowds had dispersed and it was time to undertake some daily maintenance on the heather garden. This was no more than watering the plants so that they were still fresh for the next day.

I helped out on the stand on Friday along with Richard Canovan and John Hall and again on Saturday.

I had arrived by train on the Friday and at the end of the day I joined the throngs of people heading towards Hampton Court Station. Such was the volume of people that the train was full at the start of its journey towards central London. What was of interest was the numbers of people carrying

Figure 5. The medal (© Phil Joyner 2013)

plants of all shapes and sizes on to the train. Those of a larger size were stacked in the aisles. How often do you see carriages of trains bedecked with plants?

Altogether the six days of the flower show were very intensive, yet were most enjoyable for those participating. It was a good opportunity to meet with the general public and explain to them the merits of growing heathers and how to look after them. Attendance for the six days is said to be around 124,000.

Overall, there was considerable interest generated in heathers and heather-growing as a result of the stand. It was a cost-effective way of showcasing heathers, helping to popularize them and bringing about a renaissance in the fashion for heathers and heather-growing. A big thank-you to all those who helped make this event happen, and especially to David Edge for all his devotion of time and effort to bring about an award-winning floral display.

Ericas in Mauritius, home of the dodo

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In *Heathers* 7 (2011), I wrote about the trip I did to Madagascar to hunt for some of the 45 *Erica* species endemic to the island. This was for the major project being undertaken at Stellenbosch University to analyse the DNA of as many species as possible over the whole distribution range of *Erica* in order to work out an evolutionary tree. This project was touched on by one of the project co-workers, Dr Mike Pirie, in *Heathers* 9 (2012) and by me in the talk that I gave to members attending the Annual Gathering in Falmouth in August 2012. In the talk I mentioned the big gap in our knowledge and data for around 50 species from the islands in the Indian Ocean. Fortunately we managed to get material of about 25 species on Madagascar including some possibly undescribed ones. This left us with the three species from Réunion, the two from Mauritius and the single species from the Comoros Islands (between Madagascar and Tanzania). We were in luck when a student from Réunion studying with a friend of ours in Pietermaritzburg kindly collected material of the species on Réunion.

Figure 1. Western Indian Ocean with Madagascar, showing position of Mauritius and Comoros Islands in relation to eastern Africa (Imagery © NASA 2013; TerraMetrics, Map Data © 2013 Google)

In April this year I was attending the Botanical Society's garden fair at Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden and met my friend Fay Anderson, the botanical artist who did many of the paintings in the "Baker and Oliver" *Erica* book back in the 1960s. She was looking forward to a trip with her family to Mauritius within ten days. I immediately asked her to look out for the ericas which she had seen there on a previous holiday. Then she said that the cottage they were hiring near one of the many fine beaches had two extra rooms so why didn't I join them. Well, the invitation needed no persuasion for me to accept and so I had to organise everything at very short notice. Fortunately the direct flight from Cape Town to Mauritius they were going on had a spare seat for me. One matter that was problematic was the collecting permit as mentioned in the article on Madagascar. "How could I apply just one week in advance?" was the question asked of me by the conservation officials in Port Louis wagging their heads muttering about protocol, etc. Fortunately one very charming young official took me to his office and sorted out everything.

Mauritius is a perfect holiday destination at 20°S latitude, with a subtropical climate, many gorgeous beaches and lagoons lined with coconut palms and very friendly inhabitants. It lies 830km east of Madagascar, with Réunion in between. The two small islands, the Mascarenes, are volcanic in origin with

Figure 2. *Erica mauritiensis* flowers showing the well exserted styles with large plate-like apex with the small stigmatic lobes in their centre and the very long, green, leaf-like bract in each flower (© E. G. H. Oliver).

Figure 3. *Erica brachyphylla* shrubs growing in the cleared area at le Pétrin (© E. G. H. Oliver).

Réunion still active and rising to an altitude of 3,000m. Mauritius was formed 7.8 to 6.8 million years ago and its volcanic activity ceased 25,000 years ago. Since then the volcanoes have eroded away to just 828m high in the north and on the tableland of the southwestern portion of the island. The rainfall varies from 800mm on the dry west coast to 4,000mm per annum on the tableland. Unfortunately, much of the indigenous vegetation which was mostly dense forest has disappeared since the island was inhabited around 400 years ago. Much of the land has given way to agriculture and urbanisation with vast swards of sugar cane dominating the landscape and being the main crop. With humans came the inevitable introduction of alien plants which are having a devastating effect on what is left of the indigenous flora. The worst alien for the ericas is the strawberry guava, *Psidium cattleianum*, which is a major invader on many subtropical oceanic islands. It is estimated that only 5% of the natural vegetation is left, of which only a third is regarded as good quality with few alien invaders.

Figure 4. *Erica mauritiensis* plants growing on a roadside cutting (© E. G. H. Oliver).

The heathland vegetation is restricted to shallow, well drained, rocky soils mainly on the higher parts of the tableland of the Black River Gorges National Park. Pollen studies from cores taken in a few old volcanic craters nearby show that ericas are clearly on the decline and were more dominant 900 years ago. The decline is attributed to an increase in the rainfall.

All the natural flora must have arrived on the island in the last few million years from anywhere around the Indian Ocean. The two ericas however must have come from the west, namely Réunion, Madagascar or the Africa continent because no ericas are known from Asia or Australia. Like the species on Madagascar they all used to belong in the separate genus, *Philippia*, which was characterised by small wind-pollinated flowers with an unequal calyx incorporating the bract. This latter organ may be quite large and sometimes longer than the corolla (see Figure 2). This condition has been found also in some species of *Erica* in the Cape and tropical Africa. In some cases one could find ericoid and philippioid flowers on the same plant. This led to my including *Philippia* under *Erica* in 1988 and required new name combinations and even new names (see below). The Mascarene species were dealt with in 1993.

Erica brachyphylla (the name means “with short leaves”) is very rare and restricted to just two populations. The most accessible one is right next to the office of the Black River Gorge National Park at le Pétrin. The officials there had been advised of my visit and took me to a fenced off area where the heathland vegetation is specially protected (Figure 3) through a project to remove all the aliens, especially the guavas which are abundant around the rim of the gorge. The guava grows there like wheat but is a woody plant to 4m tall. The plants are removed physically, and then Garlan herbicide is applied to the roots. Unfortunately, *E. brachyphylla* flowers in August to October but leafy material was fine for DNA extraction and the species could easily be identified without flowers – the two *Erica* species are distinguished on having leaves in threes or in fours. It formed woody shrubs up to 2m tall. With it grew *Phyllica nitida* (Rhamnaceae), a genus of ericoid shrubs well represented in the Cape Flora around Cape Town.

The other species on the island had been named *Philippia abietina* by Willdenow in Berlin back in 1809. This name could not be transferred to *Erica* since there was already an *Erica abietina* named by Linnaeus from Cape Peninsula. I therefore decided on giving it the epithet *mauritiensis*. This species is more common on the mountains, but is tucked away in places that would have to be reached by some hiking and climbing. Well, on one of our drives around the island visiting many interesting places we were driving up a road to the summit of the Black River Gorge tableland when I noticed some small erica shrublets growing on the steep road cutting near the summit (Figure 4). They turned out to be *E. mauritiensis* and were nicely in flower – not easy to see from a moving vehicle. This population turned out to be a new record for the species and the most southwestern one on the island.

This ‘holiday’ turned out to be very successful for the DNA project.

Peter Turner's “*Erica hirsuta Anglica*”

E. CHARLES NELSON

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In 1623, the Swiss botanist Caspar Bauhin of Basle listed a plant that he called *Erica hirsuta anglica* – a hairy heather from England – in his great compendium entitled *Pinax theatri botanici*, a book that, so Agnes Arber (1986) declared, was nothing less than a “complete and methodical concordance of the names of plants. It brought order out of chaos”

More than a quarter of a century later, in his brother Jean Johannes Bauhin's posthumous *magnum opus*, *Historia plantarum universalis* (Bauhin & Cherler 1650: lib. X: 358), there was an entry for *Erica anglicana parva capitulis hirsutis* which is indubitably the same plant. Jean Bauhin explained that he had received a pressed specimen of this small heather with hairy heads of flowers from Master Peter Turner, an Englishman: “... à Domino Petro Turnero Angló”. Elsewhere in *Historia plantarum universalis*, there are other references to Turner. Writing about bog myrtle (*Myrica gale*), Jean Bauhin (1650: lib. VIII: 225) recorded that around thirty years previously Peter Turner had given them a collection of pressed plant specimens from England, carefully labelled with vernacular names as well as Latin ones.

Figure 1. The memorial bust of Dr Peter Turner, St Olave's Church, Hart Street, London (left: by courtesy of Dreweatts & Bloomsbury Auctions; right © J. Harris).

PETER TURNER

“Master Peter Turner” was born in 1542, the only son of the “Father of English botany”, the Reverend Dr William Turner and his wife Jane Alder. Given that Turner senior fled England in February 1541, Peter was most probably born during his parents’ exile in Europe and surely must have wandered with them on the continent until they returned to England after the death of King Henry VIII early in 1547. A second period of exile followed the accession of Queen Mary so that between 1553 and the accession of Queen Elizabeth I in 1558, William Turner and his family settled in Germany. Of Peter’s schooling we know nothing, but he matriculated at St John’s College, Cambridge in 1564, and two years later he was at the University of Heidelberg whence he obtained a doctorate in medicine in 1571. During his time at Heidelberg, Peter went on field trips with a fellow English naturalist, Thomas Penny (c. 1530–1589), whose interests included entomology and botany. Penny reached Heidelberg sometime between 1566 and 1569 when he returned to London. Turner is known to have given Penny a specimen of a cranesbill which he had gathered near Copenhagen so he evidently knew how to press and dry plants. Again, we know nothing about Turner’s activities during the decade after he graduated but Raven (1947) noted that he must have been in Cambridge in 1575 when he was incorporated M.D. (doctor of medicine).

In late November 1581, Dr Peter Turner acknowledged that he had been practicing as a doctor in London for almost a year “against the privileges of the [Royal] College [of Physicians]”. He was prosecuted, found guilty, but was admitted as a Licentiate of the College and allowed, following payment of a fine of £30, and annual subscriptions of £2, to go on practicing medicine. He was physician to St Bartholomew’s Hospital during the 1583 plague, and was the representative for Bridport, Dorset, in two of the parliaments held during Elizabeth’s reign, in 1584 and 1585. Turner attended Sir Walter Raleigh during his incarceration in the Tower of London in March 1606.

Dr Peter Turner was 72 years old when he died on 27 May 1614. He was buried the following day in St Olave’s Church, Hart Street, London: “Maie 28. Peter Turner Doctr of phisic bur. from St, Ellens in the South Ile of ye church closs by his Father”. His widow, Pascha, commissioned a splendid monument to him with a fine, painted alabaster bust (Figs 1, 2 & 5): “half the lively figure of the party it concerneth”. After St Olave’s was severely damaged on the night of 17 April 1941 during the bombing of London, the bust from Turner’s monument “went missing” but it was recently (2013) returned to St Olave’s (Figs 2 & 5).

While greatly overshadowed, in terms of the history of botany, by his father, Peter Turner is nonetheless a significant figure because he used plant specimens that were pressed and dried, rather than just text or drawings, to convey information to others. Specifically he sent English plants, including at least one heather, to the Bauhins.

ERICA HIRSUTA ANGLICA

Over a century after *Historia plantarum universalis* was published, Carl Linnaeus (1753: 354) placed Caspar Bauhin's phrase-name *Erica hirsuta anglica* in synonymy under a new name *Erica ciliaris*, the scientific name still universally used for the heather called Dorset heath. But was Linnaeus correct in this identification? What was the plant to which Bauhin gave that name *Erica hirsuta anglica*? Can we identify this hairy English heather?

Dorset heath (*Erica ciliaris*) was among the heathers observed by the Flemish botanist Carolus Clusius (Charles de l'Écluse) during his lengthy visit to the Iberian Peninsula in 1564–1565. In *Rariorum aliquot stirpium per Hispanias observatarum historia*, Clusius (1576) described and illustrated many of the plants he had found. His eighth heath, *Erica Coris folio*, seen in Portugal and elsewhere, was Linnaeus's *E. ciliaris*. The wood-block used to print the illustration in Clusius's book was reused in several other books including his own *Rariorum plantarum historia* (Clusius 1601; as *Erica XII*), John Gerard's *The herball or generall historie of plantes* (1597), and Thomas Johnson's "very much enlarged and amended" edition of Gerard's *Herball* (1633) (see Nelson 1998). Linnaeus correctly cited Clusius's *Erica XII* under *E. ciliaris*.

However, neither of the English authors just mentioned – Gerard and Johnson – seems to have been aware that the "Chalice Heath", as they called it, occurred as a native plant in England. Yet, if *Erica hirsuta anglica* of Bauhin's *Pinax* of 1623 really was an English heather and is correctly identified as *E.*

Figure 2. Peter Turner is returned to St Olave's Church, Hart Street (photograph by Phil Manning; © 2013 St Olave Hart Street Parish Church Council).

ciliaris, then credit for “discovering” the Dorset heath in England needs to be given to Peter Turner and its discovery dated to the latter half of the sixteenth century.

In fact, *Erica ciliaris* was not admitted by most authorities as a native English species until two centuries after Bauhin’s *Pinax* was published. In 1828, the Reverend John Savery Tozer (c. 1790–1836), Curate of St Petrock in Exeter, sent a specimen, collected on “a bog near Truro”, to Dr Robert Greville (Lindley 1829). This heather was not recorded in the county of Dorset, despite its name, until 1833 when the Reverend Robert Blunt (1808–1884; later to take the name Dalby) gathered specimens on Corfe and Wareham Heaths (Bowen 2000). Even so, for more than six decades after it was recorded in Dorset, *E. ciliaris* continued to bear such book-names as “ciliated heath” or “fringed heath”, mere translations of Linnaeus’s name. It was only dubbed “Dorset heath” in the late 1890s: the first instance that I can trace of this name in print is in *The garden* on 30 April 1898 (Moon 1898; cf Robinson 1898; McClintock 1982). But I have digressed.

“C. Bauhin, mistakenly, calls it *anglica*, which has given rise to the idea of its being an English plant, but it is not,” wrote William Curtis (1800), drawing attention to an enigma without, it seems, seeking an answer. Frederic Williams (1910) followed suit, and so also did David McClintock (1966, 1980). Oddly, given his persistent inquisitiveness, David did not try to ferret out an explanation. If the ciliated/fringed/Dorset heath was unknown in England when Caspar Bauhin (in 1623) and Carl Linnaeus (in 1753) published their tomes, how can *Erica hirsuta anglica* be explained?

There is another comment that should be noted. The Reverend John Ray in his *Catalogus plantarum Angliae* (1677: 97–98), under *Erica pumila altera Belgarum* (of l’Obel) or “Low-Dutch-Heath, or Broom Heath”, wrote (translated from Latin):

Here also I think should be referred Johann Bauhin’s *Erica Anglica parva capitulis hirsutis* which he writes that he received dried from Master Peter Turner from England. In this, hairy leaves clothe the stems in four rows. The flowers [are] crowded at the tips of the shoots, large [and] pale purple. What Caspar Bauhin may mean by his *Erica hirsuta Anglica* I do not understand, since I have neither seen that species anywhere in England, nor heard from anyone else that it grows of its own accord here.

Despite Ray's denial of comprehension, which I believe has misled many of his successors including Linnaeus, he did identify Turner's plant correctly. Ray's (and P'Obel's) *Erica pumila altera Belgarum* was a name for *E. tetralix*, synonymy confirmed by Ray (1724: 471) and then by Linnaeus in his *Flora anglica* (1754: 15). Thus, I suggest that the hairy English heath, *Erica hirsuta anglica*, alias *Erica vulgaris hirsuta*, was a plant with which John Ray was quite familiar: cross-leaved heath, *E. tetralix* (Figure 4).

Bauhin and Cherler's (1650: lib. X: 358) description of the hairy English heather is not unambiguous:

Tota pulchella, vix dodrantalis, ramuli tenues, multi: folia admodum breuia, crebra, in ambitu hirsuta, ex modicis internallis seu geniculis terna vel quaterna: in summitate capitula hirsuta.

The whole [plant] dainty, scarcely 9 inches high: branchlets thin, many: leaves very short, crowded, hairy around the edges, in threes or fours at moderate intervals or nodes: at the top hairy capitula.

The first 22 Latin words could apply to the Dorset heath which has leaves with prominent hairs around their edges, arranged in whorls of three or four, and the Dorset heath could be described as dainty. The same words could also apply

Figure 3. Wood-cut depicting *Erica anglicana* ... from Bauhin & Cherler (1650: lib. X, 358).

to cross-leaved heath, although it does not usually have whorls of just three leaves. The final four words of the description refer to “*capitula hirsuta*”; the flowers of the Dorset heath are in an elongated raceme which is not noticeably hairy and would not have been termed a *capitulum*. However, the flowers of the cross-leaved heath are in an umbel which can be termed a *capitulum*, and they usually have very hairy peduncles and sepals: thus “*capitula hirsuta*” fits *E. tetralix* much better than *E. ciliaris*.

Is there any other evidence? Although a portion of the Bauhins’ herbarium has survived and is preserved in the Botanical Institute at the University of Basle, unfortunately Turner’s specimens are not among the extant sheets. However, the entry for *Erica anglicana parva capitulis hirsutis* in *Historia* was accompanied by a woodcut (Figure 3). There is no explicit evidence that this was made using Turner’s specimen, but it seems to be a unique illustration, not a previously used one as far as can be determined, so there is every likelihood that one of the Bauhins commissioned it. It shows a heather-like plant with leaves in whorls of three and four, with internodes increasing in length towards the inflorescence, and flower-buds in an umbel. It resembles the cross-leaved heath especially in its overall habit and the extending internodes.

Figure 4. Specimen of *Erica tetralix*, cross-leaved heath, labelled “*Erica vulgaris hirsutior* Common woolly Heath”, from the Bobart Herbarium (OXF), collected in the late 1600s. (© Reproduced by permission of Oxford University Herbaria.)

There is another clue. In the catalogue of the University of Oxford's *Hortus botanicus*, Stephens & Browne (1658) listed a plant named "*Erica vulgaris hirsuta*". If long-accepted synonymy is applied, any heather labelled "*Erica vulgaris*" by pre-Linnaean plantsmen should now be given the name *Calluna vulgaris* – it should be ling. However, a herbarium specimen (Figure 4) in a collection (associated with Jacob Bobart and his son, also called Jacob, who were successive curators at the Oxford garden in the mid to late 1600s, demonstrates that at that time *Erica vulgaris hirsutior* (a contemporary synonym, according to Ray (1677), of Gerard's *Erica vulgaris hirsuta*) was one of the names applied to cross-leaved heath. The English name on the same specimen is "Common Woolly Heath". Thus, the phrase-name *Erica vulgaris hirsuta* did not, as has been supposed by many authors including David McClintock (1966: 41–42), necessarily signify a hairy-leaved variety of ling. It sometimes signified cross-leaved heath.

PETER TURNER AS BOTANIST

Peter Turner is variously described as having "some knowledge of plants" (Jackson) or being an "eminent botanist" (various websites). The *Oxford dictionary of national biography* only accords him the profession of physician, adding: "Despite his introduction in his youth to botany and to natural history, there is little evidence that Turner kept up these studies in any serious way." That seems somewhat unjust, but can we assess the extent of, and date, Turner's botanical interests, or his specimens?

It may be assumed that he collected the cranesbill near Copenhagen while studying at Heidelberg – in other words, between 1566 and 1571. As Jean Bauhin died in 1613, his mention of receiving specimens "30 years ago" cannot have been later than about 1583. This suggests Peter Turner was active as a botanist mainly in his late twenties and thirties.

We do not know where else Peter Turner botanized, nor the exact places in England where he gathered the bog myrtle and cross-leaved heath. They could have come from the same locality given that both are characteristic of bog and wet heaths. As for his use of "*Gale*" for bog myrtle, Peter may have learned this from his father, either on plant-hunting expeditions with him when a lad, or from his father's books. In *The names of herbes*, published in 1548, William Turner had noted, under *Myrtus*:

Figure 5. The restored and reinstated monument to Dr Peter Turner (photograph by Phil Manning; © 2013 St Olave Hart Street PCC).

Myrtus is called in greeke myrrine, in english myrtel tree, or a myrt tree, in fre[n]ch meurte. Myrt trees grow in great plentie in Italy in the mount Appenine besyde Bonony. Some abuse a little shrub called Gal in englishe, whiche growth in fennes and waterish mores for myrto, but they are far deceyued.

The *Oxford English dictionary* does not record this use of “Gal”, only referring to the 1568 revised edition of William Turner’s *Herball* where we find this:

Of the Fen shrub or bushe called Gall. There is a short bushe that groweth in the Fenne, which is called in Duche in Netherland, Gagel, in Cambridge shyre Gall, in Summerset shyre Goul or Golle, of the Apothecaries in Englande and lowe Duchlande, Mirtillus, although it be no kinde of Myrtus, but onlye because the leaves are well smellinge and are lyke unto the leaues of wild Myrtus, sauing that they are shorter It is tried by experience that it is good to be put in beare, both me and by diverse other in Summersetshyre.

In his will, signed on 26 February 1566, William Turner left “to Peter Turner my sonne all my written bookes and yf he be a preacher all my diuinitie bookes yf he practise Phisicke all my physicke bookes ...” – that was the year Peter matriculated in Heidelberg.

Dr Peter Turner’s splendid memorial (Fig. 5) was reinstated in St Olave’s Church, Hart Street, London, on 10 June 2013.

Acknowledgements

I am most grateful to Philip Oswald for his translations of the Latin texts and his always helpful commentaries, to Colette Edwards (National Botanic Gardens, Glasnevin) for copies of references, to Gina Douglas and Lynda Brooks (The Linnean Society, London) for access to Linnaeus’s books, and to Serena Marner (Fielding-Druce Herbarium, Oxford) for the image of the sheet from the Bobarts’ herbarium. For information about the bust and its return to St Olave’s Church, I am most grateful to Charlotte Derry (Administrator, St Olave’s Church), Phil Manning (Manager, St Olave’s Church) and Dr Jim Harris (Ashmolean Museum, Oxford). For assistance with photographs, my thanks are due to Liz Peck and Poppy Walker (Dreweatts & Bloomsburgh Auctions), Phil Manning and Dr Jim Harris.

This article is an augmented and edited version of “Identifying *Erica hirsuta anglica*” originally published in *The Linnean* **24** (2): 21–25 (2008).

References

- ARBER, A., 1986. *Herbals their origin and evolution. A chapter in the history of botany 1470–1670*. Third edition. Cambridge.
- BAUHIN, C., 1623. *Pinax theatri botanici*. Basle.
- BAUHIN, J. & CHERLER, J. H., 1650. *Historia plantarum universalis*. Yverdon.
- BOWEN, J., 2000. *The flora of Dorset*. Newbury.
- CLUSIUS, C., 1576. *Rariorum aliquot stirpium per Hispanias observatarum historia*. Antwerp.
- CLUSIUS, C., 1601. *Rariorum plantarum historia*. Antwerp.
- CURTIS, W., 1800. *Erica ciliaris*. Ciliated heath. *The botanical magazine* **14**: tab. 484.
- GERARD, J., 1597. *The herball or generall historie of plantes*. London.
- JACKSON, B. D., 1877. A life of William Turner, reprinted in *William Turner Libellus de re herbaria 1538 The names of herbes 1548 facsimiles*. The Ray Society.
- JOHNSON, T., 1633. *The herball or generall historie of plantes. Gathered by John Gerarde of London ... very much enlarged and amended ...*. London. (Facsimile 1975, New York.)
- LINDLEY, J., 1829. *A synopsis of the British flora*. London.
- LINNAEUS, C., 1753. *Species plantarum*. Stockholm.
- LINNAEUS, C., 1754. *Flora anglica*. Uppsala.
- McCLINTOCK, D. C., 1966. *Companion to flowers*. London.
- McCLINTOCK, D. C., 1980. The typification of *Erica ciliaris* L., of *E. tetralix* L. and of their hybrid, *E. × watsonii* Benth. *Botanical journal of the Linnean Society* **80**: 207–211.
- McCLINTOCK, D. C., 1982. Dorset or ciliate heath. *BSBI news* no. **30**: 23.
- MOON, H. G., 1898. The Dorset heath (*Erica ciliaris*). *The garden* **53** (30 April): 364–365, plate 1168.
- NELSON, E. C., 1998. The heathers in John Gerard's *The Herball or generall Historie of Plantes* 1597–98, and Thomas Johnson's 'Very much Enlarged and Amended' edition 1633. *Yearbook of the Heather Society* **1998**: 39–54.
- RAVEN, C. E., 1947. *English botanists from Neckham to Ray*. Cambridge.
- RAY, J., 1677. *Catalogus plantarum Angliae, et insularum adjacentium*. London.
- RAY, J., 1724. *Synopsis methodica stirpium britannicarum*. London. (Facsimile 1973, The Ray Society, London.)
- ROBINSON, W., 1898. *The English flower garden*. Sixth edition. London. (Published on 1 July 1898.)
- STEPHENS, P. & BROWNE, W., 1658. *Catalogus horti botanici Oxoniensis ...*. Oxford.
- WILLIAMS, F. N., 1910. *Erica ciliaris*. *Prodromus florum britannicarum* **1**: 452–453. Brentford.

OBITUARY

BOB ROPE (1924–2013)

Bob was born in 1924, one of three children: a brother, Michael, and a sister, Jennie who survives Bob. Jennie recounts that her childhood memories were of happy holidays spent with her two brothers in mid-Wales where they stayed with their mother's aunts. At an early age Bob was already becoming interested in golf and played with (perhaps against) his father as a

member of the Shrewsbury Golf Club. Unknowingly it might have been the golf course which was his first introduction to heather. During the war years Bob served with the Royal Marines and during the latter stages of the conflict was stationed in Arthog, near Dolgellau, not far from his childhood holiday haunts.

Bob married Joan in 1951 and in 1956, after a spell in Ashbourne and Derby, they moved to their bungalow in Ravenshead, near Nottingham. Bob had started his working career in the accounts department of the then British Sugar Corporation but became a Fieldsman with that same company. He spent what he described as an enjoyable 32 years visiting the farmers, who grew the sugar beet, and dealing with the many facets of the beet cultivation including the journey of the harvested beet to the processing plant of which there were several in the Nottingham area.

Bob was fond of growing vegetables and with tomatoes, cucumbers and marrows, grown in his glasshouse, won many a prize at the local horticultural society's annual shows. Bob was also a keen rose grower and whilst the land surrounding his garden was naturally acid a heavy application of lime and phosphate, in the early years, had aided the growing of the roses and the vegetables. However after a chance purchase of heathers, presumably lime-tolerant, Bob found they grew well in his sandy soil and gradually the roses were removed and replaced with lime-tolerant heathers and in one area of the garden *Erica vagans* cultivars grew well. In 1971 he and Joan joined The Heather Society,

and such was Bob's interest in heathers and the well being of the Society he was elected to The Heather Society Council in September 1981, retiring from Council in August 2002. Bob and Joan could be described as stalwart members of the Society not only because of Bob's membership of the Society's Council but in supporting the Society through their attendances at local group meetings and in particular at conferences. Bob also helped the late Albert Julian tend the *Calluna* trials beds in the South Field at Harlow Carr after the initial trials were conducted. Bob was a generous man giving away plants to Society members who visited his garden. I remember walking away from his garden with a plant of *E. carnea* 'Rosalinde Schorn', a coloured foliage cultivar of which he was particularly fond.

Bob was very much a gentleman and always sported what I would have described as a mischievous expression. On several occasions, during the years I had the pleasure of knowing him, he would take out of his wallet an amusing snippet he had cut out of a newspaper or periodical and shared the humour with me and others. Bob described his passions as the "two G's", gardening and golf. He enjoyed his golf being a member of the Coxmoor Golf Club (described as a heathland course) and taking on the position of captain during 1969. Bob had many friends from all walks of life and was involved with Probus, the British Legion, the local church men's group, and PHAB (Physically Handicapped and Able Bodied).

In 2003 Joan passed away after a period of ill health but Bob retained his connections with The Heather Society. In the last few years Bob's failing health and his difficulty with walking meant that he was unable to tend his garden in the way he wanted, but his interest in heathers remained. Fortunately, during that period, Bob was still able to drive and managed to get around to the various local organizations he belonged to. The last few weeks of Bob's life saw him becoming house-bound relying on friends and carers to see to his needs. Bob finally passed away on 18 June 18.

His wish was to have his ashes scattered in the area where his wife's ashes were scattered, at the foot of Cader Idris, overlooking the Mawddach Estuary, close to the locations of those childhood holidays.

I would like to thank Bob's sister Jennie and her husband, Philip, for their help with this appreciation and providing the photograph. I extend The Heather Society's sincere condolences to Jennie, Philip and their family for their loss.

PHIL JOYNER

Proceedings of The Heather Society 42nd Annual Gathering, Thirsk, England, 6–9 September 2013

The 42nd Annual Gathering was well on its way to being a guaranteed success. And why not! It was September 2012, and our priceless Conference Manager, Susie Kay, was in Falmouth, taking notes on how to improve the next event. By spring 2013, guest speakers with credentials longer than the English alphabet were in place. An ancient town, worthy of our time, had been chosen as the location, complete with a hotel of antiquity and charm.

For those who still take time to cherish the good things one can find in the mailbox, springtime brings us a time to savor *Heathers: Yearbook of The Heather Society*, the quality of which cannot be surpassed. This year, with an insert of salivating proportions, we learned more about the upcoming plans for the Golden Jubilee of The Heather Society. And now, for the 170 or so members of THS who missed out on this remarkably enriching opportunity, it is time to share what you missed.

Our first glimpse of the market place in Thirsk lured visitors to the James Herriot Museum, and the gentlefolk of this Yorkshire town were going about the pleasantries of the morning. Did we mention the sun? Within minutes we were inside the Golden Fleece Hotel. After a year of planning there was absolutely nothing left for our organizer to organize. It was time simply to let the festivities begin!

All was calm, but Susie immediately vanished into the bar. Ah ha! Attempts to rescue her were too late, as her radar system had sensed the presence of Margaret and Dennis Jeskins. Her dialogue included asking about their health, acceptability of the accommodation, parking conveniences, and the quality of the food they were savoring for lunch. Weather-man, husband and personal assistant to the Conference Manager, Alan, stood at the ready to run out and tweak anything needing improvement, as he monitored the sky for signs of any suspicious clouds. Next the dining room was inspected for any flaws which might hamper the festive evening ahead. Tables were sparkling with golden confetti, mirroring the golden balloons adorning each table. The dining room was the perfect size for the 32 guests which would be celebrating in just a few hours. That would include 31 conference attendees and one guest speaker.

Next up was a stop at reception to review every room reservation with management, contemplating special needs for some of the guests and finding

the most convenient access to the rooms. While lunch was quickly eaten, secretary Alan was making mental notes of Susie's check-list. Next would be the arrival of plants and the preparation of the welcome room for the 4 o'clock tea.

Our Honorary Treasurer, Richard Canovan, soon popped into the scene, having arrived a day early to deal with a complex banking situation on behalf of THS. He reported that we could rest assured that our financial affairs were completely under control, and that hours of complex banking negotiations had, only minutes earlier, terminated in a new banking structure for the Society.

From the window of my boutique-quality room I watched as Chairman David Edge, and his unloading assistant, moved the precious cargo of heaths and heathers to the welcome room. His assistant looked very much like Alan, but he was inside helping the ladies with luggage. Susie was inside overlooking the tea and biscuits for the afternoon welcome.

The Golden Jubilee: Friday, 6 September

And so it began. At precisely 4 o'clock, the meeting room was bubbling with the most dedicated heather people to be found anywhere. The reunion for many is as devoted and caring as any family could hope for. Jean McCrindle and Diane Jones had joined ranks in Scotland and made their way to the conference. Eileen Petterssen flew in from Norway. Lin and Phil Joyner had gathered up Josey Stow in High Wycombe, and were making the conference a prelude to a longer holiday. Jean, Diane and Josey all worked side by side with their late husbands in the determination to carry out the mission of The Heather Society. Roy Nichols is a faithful attendee to conference, and did not disappoint. Our President, Professor John Griffiths, and wife Valerie were greeting the delegates, and newer members were being introduced. Annabel and Leigh Darnton were adding to their garden at Orchard House. Our local expert, Jean Preston, arrived from York. Jean spent a great portion of her life devoted to Harlow Carr Gardens, working with late husband Albert Julian.

Tea and biscuits were served, and the room was sprouting with heathers. Sales were robust. Everyone received a name badge sporting a photo of our celebratory golden Irish heath, *Erica erigena* 'Golden Jubilee', as well as a thorough packet of information to help guide us through the week-end.

Erica erigena 'Golden Jubilee' was officially registered on this very day, even as the tea was being poured. The new introduction began 28 years ago when Barry Sellers raised a few seedlings from 'Golden Lady' and planted them his

Figure 1. Susie Kay (left, standing) in conversation at dinner in the Golden Fleece Hotel, Thirsk (© E. C. Nelson).

late mother's garden. About six years ago, Susie Kay acquired some offspring from one of these plants and returned to Connemara to grow them on. Two years ago it was deemed worthy of registering, and thus the idea was born to celebrate the new plant during our Golden Jubilee. What could be more fitting! The plant is appropriately golden-leaved with a white flower. Twenty eight years should also be long enough to prove its reliability (it is not likely to revert).

By 4.30 a robust number of "Sold" signs had popped up on flats of plants, rarely found in such quality condition in the garden centers. David and Audrey Sprague had a beautiful selection of *Erica vagans* on their way to the garden in Dorking. Before the guests could properly remove the biscuit crumbs, people were congregating in the bar, and welcoming our esteemed guest speaker for the evening, Professor Mark Seaward. We were soon escorted into the festive dining room, and many of us were held in awe by some of Professor Seaward's sagas. Although very confidential, it was divulged that the professor, who has written more than 400 scientific papers concerned with bio-monitoring, urban ecology, lichens, bio-deterioration, herbaria and the history of botany, will soon be traveling to Japan as an expert advisor on the continuing problem

with nuclear power plant safety. We were intrigued to learn more about current topics of pollution causes, including some we are not addressing in the current curriculum taught at the universities. The innuendo was that human protein demands may politically imbalance the reality of large mammal pollutants. Several days later, while counting sheep in the Lake District, a haunting recollection of the discussion suggested that it may be time for such research to be openly acknowledged as an urgent need.

Soon we were congregating in the comfortable meeting room, and Chairman David Edge introduced the guest speaker who gave an illustrated account of “Two remarkable Yorkshire botanists: Richard Spruce and William Mudd”. Professor Seaward began with a warning to us all ... emphasis must be on the greater need for awareness of biodiversity and the common man versus the politicians at the helm. He quoted a favorite four-liner from John Clare:

*But be the man of science and of taste
Sees wealth far richer in the worthless waste
Where bits of lichen and a sprig of moss
Will all the raptures of his mind engross.*

Saturday 7 September: Brimham Rocks and Newby Hall

Whatever one could wish for was available on our breakfast choices at the Golden Fleece. An inviting selection of juices, yogurt, croissants and fruit was at the buffet table. Some of our friends were ordering the traditional English breakfast. Why not? The answer would come an hour later while waddling to the coach. A breakfast of sausage, eggs, black pudding, mushrooms, (was that fried bread?), bacon and tomato might make one wonder how these people stay so thin. Was “Full English” the healthy choice? Ah well, such a decadent breakfast adventure is just not the same outside the country.

In the middle of the busy Saturday market, our coach was boarding right on time. Alan assisted with the boarding. Soon we were in the Yorkshire countryside, passing through fields of freshly mown and perfectly rolled hay, many weatherproofed in white plastic, giving the appearance of giant breath mints. Perfectly clipped hedges confining flocks of sheep lead to picturesque stone cottages, many decked out in hanging baskets fit for a flower show.

Crossing over the River Ure, we were on our way to Brimham Rocks. Jean Preston explained the creation of the Millstone Grit rocks, beginning with the

Figure 2. Ling (*Calluna vulgaris*) in flower on one of the extraordinary formations at Brimham Rocks (© D. Daneri).

ice age and at a time when the area was filled with water. Erosion by rain, wind, sun and water has created whimsical shapes worthy of naming, such as Watchdog, Turtle, Dancing Bear and Druid's Writing Desk. Its elevated geology invites breathtaking views of Nidderdale and the Yorkshire Dales. Original ownership goes back to Fountains Abbey, and was sold in 1539. The property has had many owners throughout the years. The Brimham House, built after 1792 by Lord Grantly, is used today as a gift shop and information centre. Three heaths, *Erica cinerea*, *E. tetralix* and *Calluna vulgaris* can be found there, and Barry Sellers identified them all quickly during our short visit.

Soon we were on the road to Newby Hall. We were expected, and were given VIP parking. The tea room was charming, and lunch was quickly served.

This legendary home was designed by Sir Christopher Wren. In the 1700s, William Weddell enjoyed collecting Italian antiques and was fond of Chippendale and fine tapestries. Today, and for the last ten generations, the estate has been owned by the heirs of the Weddell family, and is today the house of the Compton family. In 1871, Lady Mary Vyner, daughter of Thomas

Weddell, commissioned William Burges to build the Church of Christ the Consoler after her son was killed by bandits in Greece.

The house is open to the public for half the year. The family is in residence for the remainder of the year. Famous for its perennial stroll gardens, herbaceous borders, flanked by yew trees, and the woodland walks, the garden on the banks of the River Ure, could fill hours of pleasure. During the war, the house was selected as a possible residence for the Royal Family should a retreat become necessary.

A day of beautiful weather and inspiring landscapes and aspiring gardens had been ours to enjoy.

Figure 3. The author in the double herbaceous border at Newby Hall (© D. Daneri).

“1963 and All That” or Larry the Lamb and other early members of The Heather Society

Our evening meal was offered in the conference room, and afterwards the room was transformed back into a theatre, and our Administrator, Dr Charles Nelson was introduced as speaker for the evening.

At first we thought Charles had brought the wrong lecture. He started talking about the Coal Utilization Council, and Larry the Lamb. Quickly we were seeing

Eileen Joyce at Heather Club meeting

EILEEN JOYCE, the concert pianist, was among those who attended a meeting of the Heather Society of Great Britain on Saturday, held in the grounds of Owl House, Poundgate, Buxted, by invitation of Mr. and Mrs. H. C. Ellis.

Object of the meeting was to stimulate interest in heather by encouraging amateurs to engage in the propagation of their own strains.

Various methods of propagation were discussed, and Mr. F. Stevens, of Bournemouth, an expert, supervised the taking of cuttings from the 600 established strains of heather in the grounds.

Mr. Ellis, a lawyer and founder members of the society, gave a lecture on heather, and the visitors also studied wild heather growing on Ashdown Forest, which borders the grounds of Owl House.

Sir John Charrington (chairman of the society) was present. Some of the other members had travelled from as far as Scotland.

Mrs. Ellis served refreshments.

Figure 4. Clipping from the Society's archives about the renowned pianist Eileen Joyce.

health. Instead he suggested his wife, so Constance MacLeod became our first Honorary Secretary. Colonel MacLeod, did, however, act as our first Honorary Treasurer.

Members of the founding committee included J. F. Letts, the recognized expert in heather, and an intriguing headmistress of Wateringbury Primary School, originally known as Inna Smith – in 1939 she changed her name to the double-barrelled Kellam-Smith. Miss Kellam-Smith passed away in 1968. The solicitor and playwright Henry Chandler Ellis, of Owl House, Poundgate, Uckfield, Sussex, influenced many through his extensive plantings of over 600

pictures of ships and coal barges, and then, there was one named "Lady Charrington". Ah ha, so that was it. This coal man, Sir John Charrington, liked heather. He was very influential in his business, and soon had many of his business colleagues also very interested in heather. In December 1961, Sir John published a letter in the Gardeners' chronicle touting the joys he had discovered in his personal heather garden, and suggesting the formation of a proper heather society.

On 20 February 1963, a meeting was held in the Royal Horticultural Society's New Hall Lecture Room, Westminster, London. It was unanimously decided that the (note lower case "t") Heather Society should be formed. Mr Fred J. Chappel would be the first president, while Sir John Charrington would be the first chairman. Dr Ronald Gray would become a vice-president. Dr Gray had already been growing heaths on a steep slope in Whincroft, Hindhead. The other founding vice-president was B. C. Westall Esq., owner of DeLaRue playing card company. Lieutenant Colonel Donald MacLeod had been invited to be the Honorary Secretary, but declined citing frail

Figure 5. Constance MacLeod making a presentation to Fred J. Chapple at Harlow Carr Gardens on 22 August 1971. Arnold Stow is standing behind and between Mr Chapple and Mrs MacLeod, while Josey Stow is standing to the left (with handbag) (photograph in the Society's archives).

varieties of heath and heather. At a Heather Society meeting held at Owl House, a celebrity guest was the famous pianist Eileen Joyce. F. J. Stevens of Maxwell & Beale, and also a founding committee member, led the demonstrations on the taking of cuttings.

The Society's first annual general meeting would be held on 25 September. The Chairman thanked Miss Cording for the heather floral arrangements. Miss Cording was never heard from again

The report does not tell us at what point the Heather Society became known as The Heather Society, but when the administrative offices were at Harvest House in Reading, our stationery made reference to The Heather Society. A fire later occurred at Harvest House and many records were destroyed.

In 1963 the membership of THS grew to over 200, including such aristocrats as Lord Feversham, who died before the first meeting. Sir Ronald Garvey, Lieutenant Governor of the Isle of Man was a member, as was Rear-Admiral Sir "Sandy" Gordon-Lennox, Serjeant-at-Arms of the House of Commons.

A key Coal Utilisation Council employee who was also an early member of THS was the late David McClintock, who served in intelligence during the

Second World War and rose to become Chief Accountant for the Council, from which he retired at age 60. Charles showed a 1971 photo of a presentation to Fred Chapple in Harlow Carr Gardens. Arnold and Josey Stow were in the photo. Josey attended our Golden Jubilee this year.

The Heather Society's official logo was designed in 1972 by Dick Ide (see p. 8). And lastly, a distinguished member who joined in 1964 was none other than Lady Duncan of Jordanstone ... the voice of Larry the Lamb.

Open Forum

The evening continued with a presentation by our Chairman, David Edge. The Open Forum is intended to be a time for members to speak openly about anything that comes to mind (especially heather-related topics). The hot topic of this Open Forum and for the rest of this conference was the subject of the "RHS Award of Garden Merit". The acronym AGM is not to be confused with the "other" AGM, the Annual General Meeting.

A list of the best of heaths and heather, as created by the RHS, was distributed to the delegates. David reviewed the criteria for this practical guide for the gardener to include four points, as created by the RHS: 1) excellent for ordinary use in appropriate conditions; 2) of good constitution; 3) essentially stable in form and colour; 4) reasonably resistant to pests and diseases. Immediately the question was echoed throughout the room ... "Who decided which plants made the list?" David explained that the RHS has welcomed recommendations from THS, but the concerns of the members present soon led David to conclude that we should voice our recommendations by submitting a list to Dr John Grimshaw the following morning to be passed on to the RHS.

Sunday, 8 September: The AGM, Harlow Carr, and Dr John Grimshaw & the other AGM

Finally realizing that only rugby players and other large athletes should ever order the "full English" breakfast, a gentle egg and tomato appeared at the breakfast place.

At the appointed time, the AGM was called to order. President John Griffiths thanked David Edge for his excellent organization of the Society and for his superb performance at the RHS Hampton Court Palace Flower Show this year. Not only had David gained a Silver Gilt Medal for his excellent display, but the BBC followed up with national television coverage {a segment from this

Figure 6. Group photograph at RHS Gardens Harlow Carr, 8 September 2013 (©E. C. Nelson)

programme can be viewed by visited the home-page of The Heather Society's website}. How will we measure what a great contribution this man has made on behalf of The Heather Society?

An election of officers took place, and all were recognized, as David thanked our President, Honorary Treasurer Richard Canovan, and our forever devoted member of THS, Phil Joyner, moving from Acting Secretary to Honorary Secretary who later reported that our membership has declined 5% this year. The Administrator and Editor of the *Yearbook*, Dr Charles Nelson, was also acknowledged. Charles reminded us that while we are celebrating the Society's Golden Jubilee, there were no conferences during the first eight years of organization, thus making this our 42nd Annual Gathering but 50th AGM.

The forever faithful contribution of the editor of the *Bulletin*, Daphne Everett was also acknowledged. Again, the priceless contribution of conference organizing was praised, as Susie Kay and husband Alan are given total credit. Susie remarked that next year we would be meeting in Wales. A field trip to northern Spain is also in the planning for early July 2014.

Soon the coach arrived and once again Alan magically cloned himself and appeared at ten places at one time, especially serving every need of our more

delicate members. The sunshine committee lead us to the RHS Gardens Harlow Carr. The area was once a part of the Forest of Knaresborough, a royal hunting ground. Springs were later discovered, and a formal spa established in 1840. Today the original bathhouse serves as a study center. The RHS's acquisition of the garden did not come until 2001. The Northern Horticultural Society purchased land in 1946, when a 10.5 hectare garden was intended to serve as a trial garden. It officially opened in 1950. The Heather Society approached the NHS in 1966 about establishing a heather trial. Funding was provided by Fred Chapple, and several of our late members, especially Peter Vickers and Albert Julian, were the main workers on the project. Many ladies of the THS were also devoted to the tasks of record management.

And trials they were. Acidity, drainage, a shallow clay layer, and severe occasional killing frosts have all proved challenging. Plants thought totally inappropriate for the north of England such as *Erica manipuliflora* and *E. vagans*, have fought back and flourished. A grand *Calluna* Reference Collection was established in South Field in 1980, producing a useful trial garden. They were ultimately removed by the Emmerdale pigs.

Today new heather beds have been developed in the landscape at Harlow Carr, but rose and rhododendron gardens have become more prevalent as the interests of the RHS have evolved.

A delicious buffet lunch was provided and served by Valerie Griffiths, the wife of our President, with assistance from other members. David Plumridge showed his masterful skills as the dishwasher par excellence. We also spotted a poster in the meeting room with an exquisite photo of the Plumridges' garden. The garden creator herself, Rita Plumridge, was seated near the poster.

Our afternoon speaker was Dr John Grimshaw, current director of the Yorkshire Arboretum located on the historic Castle Howard Estate.. He is a member of the RHS Nomenclature and Taxonomy Advisory Group and chairman of the RHS's Woody Plants Committee (which includes heaths and heathers). This committee, along with the Rhododendron and Camellia subcommittee, is the source of expertise for hardy trees and shrubs. John's primary plant interests lie in the African flora, while he has also recently published a book on trees recently introduced into cultivation.

In 1922, the RHS proposed an Award of Garden Merit program, but it never developed effectively. The idea was reintroduced in 1992, with the decision to review the AGM every ten years. In 2012, Dr Grimshaw was assigned the task

of co-ordinating the review. In an article in *The daily telegraph* (14 March 2013), Dr Grimshaw was quoted as saying: “Apart from a group such as heathers, where the closure of a couple of nurseries has meant a great many cultivars are no longer available, removal of 1,900 AGM’s should not be taken as worrying or negative, more that the list has been given a good pruning to remove the dead wood.” Current AGMs include 76 heaths and heathers, but the list does not include *Erica* × *griffithsii* ‘Valerie Griffiths’. A visit to the RHS website revealing the latest acceptable list includes 67 cultivars, now including this cultivar.

At the previous night’s discussion concerning the AGM, members were asked to present the Chairman with recommendations for the AGM. Dr Grimshaw re-iterated that while all decisions for candidates for the AGM are made by the Woody Plants Committee, The Heather Society is welcome to submit its recommendations for consideration.

After adjournment, there seemed to be an abundance of left-over scones. Was that Richard Canovan spotted selling them in the garden? That’s our Treasurer hard at work for the cause!

We were soon back to our charming hotel with time to socialize before our last evening meal in the lovely dining room. Maurice Everett was passing out brochures about the beautiful garden that he and Daphne had created at The Bannut. We were sad to learn that a faithful gardener had recently announced his retirement, and with that the decision was made to sell The Bannut. May the new owners be worthy of the adoption of such a magnificent creation, and may they want to share their lives and the garden with THS, as the Everetts have so graciously done.

At dinner, a great surprise awaited each member. The new ‘Golden Jubilee’ heather was presented at each place. Susie Kay and David Edge had grown the plants, all from cuttings taken in Lettergesh in Connemara. We were soon congregated back in the conference room where the final plant sales were taking place. Barry Sellers gave the history of *E. erigena* ‘Golden Jubilee’ and we were treated to a musical interlude and photos from our member from Norway, Egil Saele. His song of calling the cattle was appreciated by all, as were the photos of the heathers in his gardens; the perfectly shaped plants are not only very healthy, but are also never pruned.

Our well-known man of many hats, Alan, was now acting auctioneer for our brisk book sale of many new, old, rare and dear collector’s books concerning our favorite plant.

And so, with memories of beautiful gardens, lovely meals, reunions with cherished friends, and a time for good-byes, it could be said that “a good time was had by all”.

Monday, 9 September: a visit with Jennifer and Geoffrey Yates

Early on Monday morning, cars were packed, plants were shuffled, and the delegates headed off on separate ways. Brenda and Ronald Lord had a car-boot full of lovely plants, and was that a hard hat from exotic days working for Bechtel Corporation in Arabia? A reminder that we are indeed an eclectic group.

The work of our conference organizers was not finished. The Yateses had hoped to attend the conference and had a last-minute cancellation. A plant order needed to make its way to Windermere. Geoff is creating new heather gardens on his daughter's property. A privileged leftover passenger from Thirsk rode along for a final look at the Lake District. Could it be that we were actually stopping at Hayes Gardenworld in Ambleside! Lunch was shared as Geoff reminisced of earlier days in THS. When he had a rather large heather business, he recalled a petite young lady from Norway, coming to the garden to pick up a thousand plants for transport back to Bergen. Her name was Eileen Petterssen.

Conclusion

We came away with much to ponder, from the beginning of THS to the present. Of the aristocrats who came together originally, we have a shortage of lords and ladies and lambs named Larry. Over the last 50 years, heather awareness has become global in scope. From The Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden, Germany, Spain, the United Kingdom to Ireland, and in the United States and Canada, a small but dedicated force of heather growers and gardeners thrives. A new and rapidly growing Cape Heath industry is opening up thanks to the work being carried out in South Africa. Perhaps the capital “T” in The Heather Society has a message. Our efforts must be global, as we identify fresh eyes and new energy to secure the work that has gone before, and to assure the joy and the beauty of the heather garden in the future.

Supplement XIV (2014) to the *International register of heather names*

Registered names

Explanation of symbols

- ® Registration number, date, and name and address of registrant.
- * Description of cultivar. ◇ Origin of cultivar
- ⊗ Previously published references, if any. ⚡ Previously published images, if any.

Calluna

'Agnes'

- ® C.2013:05: registered on 25 October 2013 by J. van Leuven, Geldern-Lüllingen, Germany.
- * Bud-flowering (Knospenblüher); Kleine Knospen, dicht besetzt, gesund und wuchsig; rotlila; September–November. Foliage green; upright 50 × 50 cm after 3 years (not pruned)
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by J. van Leuven, made in 2010 between unnamed seedlings, selected in September 2011; for introduction in 2015.

'Aurelia'

- ® C.2013:03: registered on 25 October 2013 by J. van Leuven, Geldern-Lüllingen, Germany.
- * Gold foliage; broad and upright, after 3 years 40 cm tall, 60cm broad (not pruned); September–December. Besserer Wuchs als 'Sandy'; weniger Knospen, aufrechter.
- ◇ Chance sport from 'Sandy' found in October 2010 at Geldern by Johannes van Leuven; to be released in 2015.

'Elisa'

- ® C.2013:07: registered on 8 December 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Bud-flowering (Knospenblüher); buds white, 5mm long; September–December; foliage light green; bushy, broad, to 30 cm tall, to 35cm spread after 3 years (pruned).
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2008 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2009.

'Janina'

- ® C.2013:02: registered on 17 March 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Bud-flowering (Knospenblüher); buds amethyst (H1), to 5mm long; dark green foliage with paler new growth; spreading and hanging, to 10cm tall, 25cm across after 3 years (pruned).
- ◇ Sport on 'Amethyst' found by Gerhard Martens, Kalkar, in autumn 2010 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2008. Has bigger buds than 'Madonna' and is more resistant against fungi. Submitted for plant breeders right CLL 494.
- ⊗ *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 12 (December 2013): 323.

'Katja'

- ® C.2013:01: registered on 17 March 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Bud-flowering (Knospenblüher); buds white, to 6mm long; light green foliage; to 30cm × 35cm after 3 years (pruned).
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2007 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2008. Has bigger buds than 'Madonna' and is more resistant against fungi.

'Lilli'

- ® C.2011:04: registered on 16 January 2011 by K. Kramer, Edewecht, Germany
- * Bud-flowering (Knospenblüher); buds H5 (ruby), 5mm long, to 2mm diameter; July–September; foliage dark green; upright, to 30cm tall × 25cm across after 3 years (pruned). Buds show colour three weeks earlier than 'Athene' or 'Amethyst'.
- ◇ Sport on 'Loki', found by J. van Leuven, Geldern-Lüllingen, in autumn 2007.
- ⊗ *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013); *Garden Girls catalogue . . . varieties and news* 2013: 6–7.

'Lisbeth'

- ® C.2013:04: registered on 25 October 2013 by J. van Leuven, Johannes, Geldern-Lüllingen, Germany.
- * Bud-flowering (Knospenblüher); helllila, August–October; 50 × 50 cm after 3 years (not pruned). Eine wuchsig und früh (ab Mitte August); foliage grün-grau; aufrecht.

- ◇ Deliberately raised from two unnamed seedlings, cross made by J. van Leuven in August 2010; selected in August 2011; to be released in 2015

‘Mary Lu’

- Ⓢ C.2013.06: registered on 8 December 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Bud-flowering (Knospenblüher); buds white, to 6mm long; light green foliage; to 30cm × 35cm after 3 years (pruned).
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2007 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2008. Has bigger buds than ‘Madonna’ and is more resistant against fungi.

Daboecia

‘Rosella’

- Ⓢ D.2013.01: registered on 17 March 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Corolla shell-pink (H16) (without blue), June–October; foliage mid-green; upright to 30cm tall, 25cm spread after 2 years (pruned)
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2005 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2010.
- Ⓢ *Garden Girls catalogue ... varieties and news* [2013]: 19 [name only].

‘Angelina’

- Ⓢ D.2013.02: registered on 17 March 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Corolla ruby (H5), June–October; foliage mid-green; upright to 30cm tall, 25cm spread after 2 years (pruned)
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2005 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2010. More floriferous than ‘Amelie’.
- Ⓢ *Garden Girls catalogue ... varieties and news* [2013]: 19 [name only].

‘Antonia’

- Ⓢ D.2013.03: registered on 17 March 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Corolla ruby (H5), June–October; foliage mid-green; upright to 30cm tall, 25cm spread after 2 years (pruned)
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2005 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2010. More floriferous than ‘Amelie’.

‘Rieke’

- Ⓢ D.2013.04: registered on 17 March 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Corolla lavender (H3), June–October; foliage mid-green; upright to 30cm tall, 25cm spread after 2 years (pruned)
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2005 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2010. More floriferous than ‘Vanessa’.

Erica

‘Golden Jubilee’: *E. erigena*

- Ⓢ E.2013.02: registered on 6 September 2013 by B. Sellers, London.
- * “Golden” foliage; white flowers, corolla 5–6mm long, to 2mm across, ovoid; calyx 3–4mm
- ◇ Selected seedling from ‘Golden Lady’, propagated from an individual plant growing in the garden of Susie and Alan Kay, Letterfrack, County Galway, Ireland. Another plant in Seller’s mother’s garden was 1m tall unpruned after 29 years.

‘Pink Magic’: *E. × darleyensis*

- Ⓢ E.2013.03: registered on 8 December 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Corolla heliotrope (H12; RHSCC 73B), December–May; mature foliage mid-green, new growth bright green; bushy, broad, to 40cm tall, 40cm spread after 3 years (pruned)
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2007 between unnamed seedlings, selected in 2011. Individual flowers larger than ‘Winter Treasure’.

‘Spring Light’: *E. × cavendishiana* (Cape heath)

- Ⓢ E.2013.01: registered on 17 March 2013 by K. Kramer, Edewecht-Süddorf, Germany.
- * Corolla yellow, May–June; foliage mid-green; upright, to 30cm tall, 20cm spread after 2 years (not pruned)
- ◇ Deliberately raised cross by Kurt Kramer, made in 2003 between unnamed seedlings, both from *E. × cavendishiana* ‘Gengold’ (*E. nana × patersonii*), selected in 2008. More floriferous than ‘Gengold’ and upright in habit.

Other names new to the Registrar

Andromeda polifolia

'Blue Lagoon'

- * Clear blue-grey, linear-lance-shaped leaves, 2–3 cm long, with silvery hues; urn-shaped soft pink flowers (April–May[–early June]). Differs from 'Blue Ice' in much more prominent blue-grey foliage, rather than blue-green.
- ◇ Sport on 'Blue Ice, discovered by Marcel Brand at Boskoop, Netherlands, in 2006; in 2010, patented under United States PP22004.
- ☒ CPVO and other websites.

Calluna

1) Names of cultivars recently granted plant breeders rights.

'Annesofie': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Dorota': CLL 382: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Emma': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Fabiola': CLL 411: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Freya': CLL 410: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013); *Garden Girls catalogue ... varieties and news* 2013: 6.

'Georgina': CLL 455: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Harmke': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Ida': CLL 473: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Lotti': CLL 456: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Madelon': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Madlen': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Mandy': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Nadja': CLL 412: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Neelma': CLL 386: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Philipine': CLL 388: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013)..

'Red Moon': CLL 405: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Renate': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Rilana': CLL 387: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Sabina': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Samara': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Sanne': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Saphira': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Sarah': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Savannah': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Sissi': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Suske': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Tatjana': CLL 389: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Trudi': CLL 460: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Vaika': CLL 458: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Valeska': CLL 459: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Vasya': CLL 457: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'Vedette': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'WI 12011': CLL 461: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'WI 52011': CLL 462: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'WI 62011': CLL 463: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

'WINK 12009': CLL 406: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 83 (2013).

2) Proposed denominations for clones submitted for plant breeders' rights

'Barcelona': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Havanna': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'La Luna': CLL 483: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 45 heft 12 (December 2013): 385.

'Lunoarctic': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Lunokarmin': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

- 'Monaco': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.
 'Oslo': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.
 'Pretoria': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014
 'Riga': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.
 'Stockholm': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.
 'Sydney': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.
 'Verona': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.
 'Virginie': Bundessortenamt website, accessed 21 December 2005, 4 September 2006.
 'Weißer Michael': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.
 'WI 12013': CLL 491: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 8 (August 2013): 170.
 'WI 52013': CLL 492: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 8 (August 2013): 170.
 'WI 62013': CLL 493: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 8 (August 2013): 170.

3) Other names

'Darkness Gelb'

- * Bronzeblaublauge Mutante aus 'Darkness'. Blüte einfach purpurrot.
- Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 83.

'Hilda'

- * Flower buds 75A–74C (H3-11)
- ◇ From Helmut & Thomas HiedlGBR; granted CPVR 24 November 2008.
- *Garden Girls catalogue . . . varieties and news* 2013: 6, 12.

'Keine Chance': *TASPO magazin special 2011*: 6.

'Luisa'

- * Buds RHS CC 70A–74B (H9–H10).
- ◇ From Helmut Hiedl
- *Garden Girls catalogue . . . varieties and news* 2013: 6.

'Lukas Weiße'

- * Laubzierende Besenheide, leuchtend gelbes Laub, straff aufrechter Wuchs.
- Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 83.

'Saint Kilda Minty White'

- * ungewöhnlich frühe Blütezeit Juli/August, kriechender Wuchs, strahlend weiße einfache Blüte, frischgrünes
- Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 86.

'Saint Kilda Minty Yellow'

- * mattenförmiger Wuchs, zitronengelbgrünes Laub, ungewöhnlich frühe Blüte Juli/August, Blüte einfach weiß
- Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 86.

'Silver Sensation'

- * Silver foliage, white flowers.
- ◇ Grown by Daphne Everett (The Bannut) in 2012; obtained from John L. Jones (Glynwern Heather Nursery, Lampeter, Wales) many years previously.

Beauty Ladies: registered trade mark.

'Beauty Star': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Million' (error for 'Mullion'): *Détente jardin* no. 86: 8 (caption) (November–December 2010).

'Mont Blanc': CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Sina': *TASPO magazin special 2011*: 23; CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

'Skyline': *TASPO magazin special 2011*: 6.

'Verenka': *TASPO magazin special 2011*: 27.

Daboecia

‘Grace Omalley’

- ◊ DAB 10; submitted for PBR on 15 February 2012; granted 16 December 2013; by Holger Lienhop, Verden.
- ☒ *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 45 heft 5: 108 (May 2012).

‘Rosabella’: DAB 13: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 45 heft 9 (September 2012): 239; __46 heft 2 (February 2013): 41.

*Erica**E. carnea*

‘Gelbe Nathalie’:

- * Winterheide mit kupfrig gelber Winterlaubfärbung, Blüte leuchtend purpurrot.
- ☒ Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 90.

‘Kramers Spate’

- * purpurrot spätblühend März/April, Wuchshöhe 30 cm.
- ◊ Züchtung Kurt Kramer, Süddorf, Germany.
- ☒ Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 90.

‘Maxime’

- * rubinrosa raschwüchsige Verbesserung von *E. carnea* ‘Winter Beauty’, Blütezeit Februar/März
- ◊ Selektion der Fa. de Vries.
- ☒ Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 90.

‘Weiße Perle’

- * reinweißblühende Winterheide, Neuheit.
- ☒ Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 91.

E. cinerea

‘Ockham’

- * No flowers, instead each flower is replaced by a dark ruby (H5) bud-like cluster of c. 20 “bracts” having shape and texture of sepals.
- ◊ Noticed about 2004 on Ockham Common, Surrey, by James Adler (Ranger) and subsequently (2006) propagated at RHS Garden Wisley; planted in Howard’s Field at Wisley; introduced by Forest Edge Nursery, Wimborne, Dorset, in 2013.
- ☒ *RHS plant finder* 2013 [name only].

E. × darleyensis

‘Eva’s Gold’ (typographic error): Baumschule H. Hachmann, *Vorrats- und Preisliste für den Wiederverkäufer (Herbst 2011. Frühjahr 2012)* [pdf]: 91.

‘Geo. Randell’ (typographic error): Catalogue, Waihi Nursery, Waihi (New Zealand), 5 (not dated, c. 1965).

‘Ruth’

- ◊ ERI 114: granted plant breeders right on 20 May 2011.
- ☒ *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 85 (2013).

‘Snow Surprise’: *RHS plant finder* 2013 [name only].

‘Tyann’: CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

- ◊ from Pépinières Renault; plant breeders right rejected on 26 April 2011.

‘Tylou’.

- * Bushy, with light green foliage, flowers lilac-pink to heliotrope (H11).

- ◇ ERI 168: from Pepinieres Renault; granted plant breeders right on 26 April 2011.
- ⊞ CPVO website accessed 5 January 2014.

Cape heaths

E. gracilis: names of cultivars recently granted plant breeders rights.

- 'Alexandra': ERG 132: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Amalia': ERG 129: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Annabelle': ERG 176: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Astrid': ERG 137: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Carmen': ERG 138: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Catherine': ERG 177: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Charlotte': ERG 130: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Desiree': ERG 139: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Estelle': ERG 185: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Friederike': ERG 124: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Helena': ERG 171: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Jan': ERG 178: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Karoline': ERG 131: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Katharina': ERG 175: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Käthe K': ERG 186: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Kleopatra': ERG 133: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Leonore': ERG 184: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Rania': ERG 172: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Salma': ERG 173: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Sirikitt 2': ERG 128: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Sven': ERG 181: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Viktoria': ERG 134: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).
- 'Wilhelmine': ERG 125: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 Sortenregister: 84 (2013).

Proposed denominations for other cultivars of Cape heaths recently submitted for plant breeders rights.

- 'Autumn Star': ERR 121, *E. mammosa*: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 4 (April 2013): 81.
- 'AW 1007': ERG 187, *E. gracilis*: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 3 (March 2013): 60.
- 'AW 1008': ERG 188, *E. gracilis*: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 3 (March 2013): 60.
- 'AW 1053': ERG 189, *E. gracilis*: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 3 (March 2013): 60.

Denomination for clone withdrawn

- 'Blanka': ERG 183, *E. gracilis*: *Blatt für Sortenwesen* 46 heft 11 (November 2013): 308.

CORRIGENDUM to *Heathers* 10 (2013)

The figures in the article on slime moulds were mis-numbered, and the sequence was incorrect.

Left image is correctly Figure 1: *Leocarpus fragilis* growing on cross-leaved heath (*Erica tetralix*).

Right image is correctly Figure 2: *Leocarpus fragilis* with sporocarps, on bell heather (*Erica cinerea*).